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Executive Summary

The MIXED project explored the resilience, efficiency, and sustainability of Mixed Farming and Agroforestry Systems (MiFAS) across farms, landscapes, and value chains in Europe. Findings show that MiFAS can enhance resource use efficiency, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and improve resilience to climate change through diverse agricultural activities that promote synergies thereof, e.g. nutrient cycling. MiFAS both at farm and territorial level are found to have potential to improve circularity and resilience while supporting sustainability goals, although profitability and labour efficiency vary depending on context. MIXED highlights that the efficiency and resilience of MiFAS are highly context-specific, influenced by local conditions and socio-economic contexts. Evaluations at farm and landscape level showed different results and indicated that other specificities also need to be taken into account, e.g. at the sub-national level, in natural conditions, in traditional practices and in the resulting cultural landscapes. Besides rather common examples of MiFAS' setups in Austria, Denmark, France, Germany, the Netherlands, Portugal, Switzerland and the United Kingdom, additional case studies from Poland, Germany, and Romania highlight the adaptability and environmental benefits of MiFAS.

The transition to MiFAS confronts farmers and the larger agri-food system with both general and transition-specific challenges. Among the latter are barriers such as a need for cultural shifts and high initial investments, as well as systemic inertia due to entrenched large-scale monoculture practices. Other challenges may persist beyond the transition, chiefly profitability concerns which arise from inadequate market compensation for MiFAS products and subsequent conflicts between short-term economic goals and long-term sustainability, as well as labour demands and regulatory barriers. Furthermore, there are technical issues such as the need for specialised machinery, as well as knowledge gaps in diversified farming, and limited advisory support. Regulatory frameworks often present increased administrative burdens and legal uncertainties for mixed farms. Weak integration into supply chains, insufficient remuneration of public goods provided and increased costs incurred by MiFAS, both by the markets and public funding, as well as lack of understanding of MiFAS benefits in society further hinder adoption.

The methodological approach of T6.4b in the MIXED project involved three interconnected phases to develop policy recommendations for MiFAS. Phase 1 focused on data collection through back casting workshops, a policy instruments database, and an analysis of the EU's CAP Catalogue of Interventions to identify challenges, gaps, and opportunities. Phase 2 involved the development of draft policy recommendations through preparatory workshops, interactive online sessions with MiFAS networks, and the use of Miro boards to assess political objectives, key support factors, and existing policy instruments. In Phase 3, the draft recommendations were refined through result-mining workshops of results of different work packages (WPs), internal project meetings, and a final policy workshop in Brussels with stakeholders from political, civil society, and farming organizations to align recommendations with current political discussions and decision-making processes. Policy recommendations from the MIXED project involve integrated, science-based, and collaborative approaches to promote sustainable, resilient, and economically viable mixed farming and agroforestry systems (MiFAS) across the EU. Systemic policy changes, improved funding mechanisms, capacity building, and increased public and institutional awareness of the environmental, economic, resilience and social contributions of MiFAS are cornerstones of the recommendations.

Key strategies include enhancing research funding to close knowledge gaps on long-term benefits of MiFAS, fostering transdisciplinary research with strong farmer participation, and establishing peer to peer knowledge-sharing networks. Capacity-building initiatives should revise vocational training to focus on holistic, system-based learning and strengthen advisory services for diversified farming practices. Landscape-level strategies are recommended, in order to encourage regional cooperation, supported by intermediaries facilitating collaboration among stakeholders. The project results

underscore the critical role of intermediary organisations in supporting transitions to MiFAS. Regulatory frameworks must be simplified to reduce administrative burdens for diversified land use practices, align with long-term stable policies that are sufficiently flexible to accommodate diverse MiFAS practices but nonetheless ensure overarching regulatory goals. Financial support should target both, the transition phase during the establishment as well as the ongoing management of MiFAS, through investment grants, compensation for the provision of public goods, and support for cooperative approaches to improving the market position of mixed farms.

Transition pathways to resilient and efficient MiFAS involve removing barriers, supporting new systems, and engaging multi-level governance. The future Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), as envisioned in the Strategic Dialogue on the Future of EU Agriculture, must shift toward a stronger focus on sustainability. The findings of the MIXED project show how mixed farming and agroforestry can contribute toward this transformation. Implementing the presented policy recommendations in the CAP as well as in national and regional policy arenas can enable a transition to more mixed farming and agroforestry in the EU.

Alongside to the CAP, other instruments can support the transition to mixed farming and agroforestry. One example is the tax on greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from agriculture that was recently introduced by Denmark. As this is an unprecedented instrument in the agricultural sector, its effects are still largely unknown and only simulations offer the possibility of analysing the potential impact of such a tax on agricultural production. Although there is considerable variation, a simulation based on data from Swedish dairy farms suggests that an emissions tax is likely to negatively affect farmers' profits, on the one hand, while reducing GHG emissions and leading to more mixed farming and agroforestry systems, on the other.

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Acronyms

AFS	Agroforestry System (sing./plur.)
BC-WS	Back casting workshop (followed by network code, see Table 1)
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy (of the European Union)
D	Deliverable
DEA	Data Envelopment Analysis
EBAF	European Board on Agriculture and Food
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FADN	Farm Accountancy Data Network
FES	Farm Economic Survey
FSDN	Farm Sustainability Data Network
GHG	Greenhouse gas (sing./plur.)
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
LCA	Life-Cycle Assessment (sing./plur.)
MFF	Multiannual Financial Framework (of the EU)
MiFAS	Mixed Farming and Agroforestry System (sing./plur.)
RM-WS	Result-mining workshop (followed by MIXED work package code)
WP	Work Package

Introduction

The objective of **Work Package 6 (WP6)** of the MIXED project was to assess the impacts of implementing mixed farming and agroforestry systems (MiFAS) at different scales in terms of resilience, efficiency, climate change mitigation and provision of further public goods in a broader context. The specific tasks were to develop an integrated assessment framework for analysing efficiency and resilience at different scales (T6.1), to assess these factors at farm level (T6.2), to extend the analysis to higher levels such as regional, national and/or EU levels (T6.3), and to examine the role of policy instruments in supporting or hindering the transition to more MiFAS (T6.4). Based on factors such as natural resources, climate and system functions, best practices for efficient and resilient MiFAS differ between regions. To address this issue, assessments have been carried out in different MiFAS contexts using both top-down and bottom-up approaches:

Therefore, **Task 6.4** consisted of two parts to 'assess the role of policy instruments in transition scenarios'.

A bottom-up approach adopted participatory techniques, involving local stakeholders and experts in workshops and consultations to identify key factors that hinder or enable the transition to mixed production patterns and to develop five thematic clusters of policy actions. **The objective was the development of policy recommendations, to be found in the chapter titled '[Policy Brief](#)'.**

The other part used a top-down approach to simulate the fiscal instrument of a greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions tax. This supported the assessment of trade-offs and synergies between cost-effective GHG mitigation and MiFAS.

The main focus of this deliverable is on the work done in relation to the bottom-up approach, presented in the chapter '[Policy recommendations for a transition to efficient, resilient and sustainable Mixed Farming and Agroforestry Systems](#)'. A brief extract of the work on the top-down approach is presented in the [last chapter](#).

The empirical work of MIXED is based on extensive data collection in 14 networks representing different types of MiFAS. These are referred to throughout this report using the below country codes.

Table 1: Networks in the MIXED project

code	Network
Agroforestry	
AT	Poultry production (laying hens) integrated in fruit production/orchards
CH	High stem fruit trees mixed with livestock and cereal production
DK1	Pig and dairy production integrated in energy crop production; local pig breeds integrated in fruit/nut production.
DE2	Integrated agroforestry, grassland and livestock systems
FR1	Pigs integrated in agroforestry systems and cooperation with arable farmers to provide local produced feed sources
PT	Integrated production of pasture, cork and high value meat products based on local pig, cattle and sheep breeds
Regional cooperation	
DK2	Manure/grass protein exchange within a network of livestock and arable farmers
FR2	Crop and livestock/manure exchange between farms to produce beef fed on local produced feed sources

code	Network
NL	Land and manure exchange within a network of arable and dairy farmers
UK1	Grazing cattle/fodder exchange within a network of beef suckler herds and arable farmers (East↔West Scotland)
UK2	Grazing sheep/fodder exchange within a network of livestock and arable farmers (foraging winter cereals)
Other MiFAS case studies	
DE1	(Re)wetting of arable land, exchange of land between arable and livestock farmers
RO	Integrated livestock, natural pastures and trees supporting agritourism
PL	One farm (< 2000 ha, 150 employees) with agriculture and product processing. Agroforestry in pasture and crop systems.

Policy recommendations for a transition to efficient, resilient and sustainable Mixed Farming and Agroforestry Systems

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A summarizing version of the following chapters has been submitted and is currently under review for publication in the journal *EuroChoices*. Holger Pabst, Johannes Lang, Simone Sterly: Navigating Europe's Agricultural Transition: Systemic Policy Approaches to Mixed Farming and Agroforestry

1 Methodological approach

The methodological approach of T6.4b comprised a series of interconnected stages, as illustrated in Figure 1. Initially, a comprehensive collection and analysis of essential information pertaining to policy aspects associated with the MiFAS of the MIXED networks (see Table 1) and countries (Austria, Denmark, France, Germany, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Switzerland, The Netherlands and United Kingdom) was conducted. This analysis was undertaken with a view to identifying gaps, challenges and opportunities for further development. This formed the basis for an initial draft of recommendations, which were then refined by considering further findings from the networks and the results of the other WP. The final recommendations are presented in this report. The subsequent sections elaborate on the individual work phases and activities.

Figure 1 Stepwise approach to infer policy recommendations

1.1 Phase 1: Data and information collection

1.1.1 Back casting workshops

Deliverable D1.1, titled 'MiFAS 'state-of-the-art' and future scenarios in selected European regions', provides a summary of the participatory back casting workshops conducted with all networks in 2021. The back casting method facilitated discussions on potential bottom-up transition pathways to future sustainable mixed farming systems, with a particular focus on the farmers in the networks. The deliverable was evaluated in terms of its relevance to MiFAS policy, encompassing challenges, barriers and enabling factors. The findings were structured according to the identified key policy areas (administration and regulation, (public) funding, knowledge and training, other), which were subsequently discussed with the project consortium. The results of the back casting workshops are referred to in the following as 'BC-WS xyz', where 'xyz' is the code for the network or country concerned.

1.1.2 Policy instruments database

The key policy areas previously identified in the back casting workshops informed the design of an online survey to record existing policy instruments in relation to the different networks in MIXED. The survey and accompanying guidelines were finalised in January 2023, and a follow-up online tutorial was held on 9 February (a recording was made available to all MIXED partners). As far as was reasonable, a minimum of five beneficial policy instruments per network were to be recorded by mid-May (subsequently extended to the end of July). The responsibility for this task was assigned to the academic partners, but there was also the option of disseminating the survey to network partners and external policy experts. Where feasible, closed questions or pre-defined options were utilised to facilitate more straightforward analysis.

In addition to the titles of the instruments and their categorisation according to the key areas, the survey encompassed the thematic domains addressed, for instance, agriculture, biodiversity, the environment or trade. Furthermore, the survey included questions concerning the level of implementation, whether at the regional, national, or EU level. The central questions of the survey were directed towards an understanding of the function and mode of action of the respective instruments. Additionally, the questionnaire addressed the innovative aspects of the respective instruments, as well as potential synergies with other political approaches and strategies. Respondents were invited to evaluate the potential of the instrument to exert a favourable influence on the future development of the respective MiFAS. The survey concluded with the option to provide feedback on any potential negative or obstructive aspects.

Following the closure of the online survey at the end of July 2023, the data was subjected to analysis regarding the network themes, the instruments' key policy area (e.g. funding), as well as emerged challenges. In a few cases, consultations were held with the relevant contact persons. The results were summarised in an internal report on the policy instruments database.

1.1.3 CAP Catalogue of Interventions

The above database of policy instruments was limited to the MIXED countries and focused exclusively on the thematic aspects of the networks. Furthermore, the focus was on instruments that could positively influence the development of the respective networks, while negative aspects and gaps in the instrument mix were only mentioned occasionally and/or in bilateral discussions. On this basis, the CAP Catalogue of Interventions published online by the EU¹ was scanned in the second half of

¹ European Commission – DG for Agriculture and Rural Development: CAP Catalogue of Interventions. available online at https://agridata.ec.europa.eu/extensions/DashboardCapPlan/catalogue_interventions.html

2023 for thematically relevant interventions for MiFAS and on the network themes of agroforestry, cooperation, rewetting, agritourism, etc. In particular, the aim was to broaden the scope to include other EU Member States and to identify gaps in the mix of instruments and funding frameworks. The information gathered then provided important insights for phase 2, the development of policy recommendations.

1.2 Phase 2: Development of policy recommendations

1.2.1 Preparatory workshop during project meeting in Toulouse, FR

With the aim to initiate the development of policy recommendations, and to sensitise partners for the policy relevance of research findings, a workshop with all project partners was conducted during the project meeting in Toulouse in September 2023. The partners discussed the key factors that determine the efficiency and resilience of a MiFAS, the motivation of the farmers as well as the factors that have a positive or negative impact on the uptake of MiFAS. Results were documented and used in the preparation of the next steps, i.e., the development of the structures of the Miro Boards for the policy workshops and the result mining tables.

1.2.2 Online policy workshops with networks

The policy instrument database and the screening of the CAP Catalogue of Interventions served two primary objectives: first, to provide insights into existing policy instruments regarding the respective networks, and second, to identify and assess interventions implemented by other countries, with a view to adaptation in the MIXED context and countries. Given the notable discrepancies in the depth and quality of information available in the policy instrument database across the networks, there was a clear need for supplementary data collection efforts.

To obtain further information pertinent to the formulation of policy recommendations, separate interactive online workshops were conducted with the networks during the early months of 2024. The plan entailed the organisation of three online workshops on the network themes of 'agroforestry', 'regional cooperation' and 'other' (which included the participation of MIXED' special networks in Germany and Romania). Despite repeated attempts, no suitable date could be identified for the workshop on 'regional cooperation'.

The workshops were structured in three steps and facilitated using Miro boards².

- 1) To ascertain the political objectives and steering factors at play, participants were asked whether any political will and/or objectives exists in the countries to support and strengthen agriculture in accordance with the respective networks' thematic focus. Furthermore, the aim was to gain the networks' insights as to where they see the greatest relevance and need for support.
- 2) The second stage involved the identification of key elements or factors that could serve to bolster the MiFAS. These elements were then assessed and ranked in consideration of their respective potential impact.
- 3) The third step involved the exchange of views on the existing enabling and supporting policy instruments of the respective countries. The objective was to develop practical ideas and approaches relating to areas including training and capacity development, communication, administration, investment and subsidies, as well as the value chain.

² Miro is a collaborative online whiteboard platform that teams can use to visually brainstorm, plan projects, and work together in real time.

Based on the responses received from the networks, the initial draft policy recommendations were formulated through this bottom-up approach.

1.3 Phase 3: Result mining with MIXED WPs and refining policy recommendations

1.3.1 Online result mining workshops with MIXED WPs

To provide scientific support for refining the draft policy recommendations, a result mining workshop was held for each of the MIXED WPs during June and July 2024. While the WP leads were obliged to attend, other partners and individuals engaged in the project, along with those contributing to the respective WPs, were also invited to participate. The result mining workshops utilised a two-step approach, initially focusing on the efficiency and resilience of MiFAS (either in general or specific to MiFAS) and subsequently considering the implications of the results of the respective WP in this context. In the second phase, the discussion centred on the results of the individual WPs and how they support the draft policy recommendations. In addition to the project results available in the form of deliverables and publications, further evidence was gathered from external sources to support the project's findings. Although the result mining workshops yielded valuable insights, in parts these were not (yet) grounded in scientific evidence, as many tasks were still in progress, but rather reflected preliminary assessments of the researchers involved.

The analyses in the individual WPs were not finalised at the time of the result mining workshops, due to delays in the project. Therefore, drafts and interim results had to be used for the further elaboration of the policy recommendations, rather than relying fully on final outcomes and publications. This report reflects the latest results as far as possible. The results of the result mining workshops are referred to in the following as 'RM-WS xy', where 'xy' is the WP concerned.

1.3.2 Internal policy workshop during project meeting in Basel, CH

A meeting of the MIXED project was held in Basel in September 2024 and was used to review and generally prioritise the proposed policy recommendations within the project consortium. This task also included developing and suggesting specific actions that could contribute to the implementation of the policy recommendations.

1.3.3 MIXED Policy Workshop 'Mixedness in European Agriculture – hot topics for policy makers' in Brussels, BE

The policy recommendations, including specific actions, were available in a largely harmonised form after the workshops with the WPs and the project consortium. As part of WP7, a policy workshop was organised in Brussels on 3 December 2023 to discuss and fine-tune the recommendations. Stakeholders from political institutions were invited in addition to civil society organisations and farmers' organisations. The main purpose of the workshop was to reflect on the prepared recommendations, to harmonise them with the political decision-makers and to relate them to the current political discussions.

2 MIXED findings on resilient, efficient and sustainable MiFAS

The MIXED project aims to 'support the development of European Mixed Farming and Agroforestry Systems (MiFAS) that optimise efficiency and resource use, reduce GHG emissions, and show greater resilience to climate change by considering agronomic, technical, environmental, economic,

institutional, infrastructure and social advantages and constraints'. As required by different objectives, data and approaches, different work packages and deliverables in the MIXED project have employed different definitions and operationalisations of MiFAS, of resilience and of efficiency. In so far as they are crucial to the findings that follow, these definitions are summarised in the first section of this chapter. The development of policy recommendations (4) was informed by an understanding of factors influencing efficiency and resilience of a MiFAS in a specific context and at different levels and/or from different perspectives as laid out below. In MIXED we look at the farm level, at a landscape/regional level, at specific value chains, and at a European (territorial) level.

The efficiency and resilience of different MiFAS have been assessed in the MIXED project at farm level, at landscape level, and at value chain level. The sections following the brief introduction of key concepts summarise the findings of MIXED regarding sustainability, resilience and efficiency at the different levels.

2.1 Key concepts of the MIXED project

Fundamental understandings of **mixedness** for the MIXED project were defined in D6.1.

'A MiFAS at the farm level consists of a diversity of activities (e.g., crop, livestock, forestry) which are carried on promoting interactions among them. Interactions come in the form of shared resources, shared inputs, complementarity among fluxes with the overall aim of closing the N, C, P cycles. Complementarity can occur in different forms, for example by-products from an activity can be used as inputs for another (e.g., whey used to feed pigs); products of an activity can be used as input for other activities (e.g., grain used to feed pigs or manure to fertilize crops). Finally, complementarity can occur also among niches (e.g., co-grazing species with different preferences.'

More concrete understandings and operationalisations of mixedness at the farm level have taken different forms, according to the various objectives in different parts of the project. The Eurostat farm typology was used in D3.3 and other analyses. Among the nine farm types, three are mixed: mixed cropping, mixed livestock, and mixed crop-livestock.

Some of the systems under closer scrutiny in the networks are **mixed at the farm level**. These are, i.e., the various agroforestry systems, integrated farming in Poland, small farms in Romania, the Montado in Portugal. Mixedness at a landscape level is the result of inter-farm cooperation (even though cooperating farms may well be mixed in themselves as well).

Mixedness at the landscape level is understood as 'a system of farms in which farmers interact among themselves and with other actors, resulting in improved circularity at that level' (D6.1, p. 9). While these interactions may be facilitated by specific ecological conditions and administrative homogeneity, 'landscape' neither must be congruent with an administrative region, nor with an ecoregion or similar definitions of landscape. Definitive boundaries are not essential. This concept is meant to introduce a territorial perspective, to study and practically facilitate mixedness at a spatial scale that exceeds the individual farm and includes social and ecological consequences beyond the farm. The holistic perspective on the landscape also engenders identifying possible synergies and problems, setting goals, strategising, and, in facilitating *ownership* of the landscape, overcoming problems of collective action. In a landscape view, costs that would be external to the farm economy perspective are internal to the system in question. This is to say a shift to the landscape perspective brings about both means and incentives to tackle negative externalities.

For analytical purposes in the MIXED project, mixed landscapes were delineated in different ways. D3.3, D6.1, and parts of D6.3 deal with this, and develop a definition and operationalisation for mixed landscapes at NUTS 2 level, as data availability in that case required adherence to administrative

boundaries. On the other hand, in the Dutch network and innovation study on cooperating farms, the lands of the cooperating farms defined the boundaries of the landscape under consideration (D2.4).

When landscape levels are analysed, mixedness is determined using agricultural land-based indicators. A landscape is considered mixed if the diversity of livestock and crop activities exceed a certain threshold (D3.3, p. 19, 25 f.). For the analyses reported in D6.3, as a measure of **circularity**, a simplified gross nitrogen balance was introduced into the operationalisation of mixed landscapes (D6.3, p. 5).

Following Meuwissen et al. (2019), **resilience** is understood 'as the ability of a MiFAS to provide the functions of sustainability over the long term despite challenges and disturbances' (D6.1, p. 16). At the landscape level, this means that 'resilience is about the capacity of the landscape to adapt and recover from disturbances' (D6.3, p. 4). Resilience at the farm level is a variable in some analyses conducted during the MIXED project, and is operationalised, based on Meuwissen et al. (2019), 'as a composite indicator of robustness, adaptability, and transformability' (D6.2, p. 2).

Efficiency is about 'optimal utilization of resources, minimising waste, and enhancing productivity' (D6.3, p. 4). Different resources or inputs, as well as outputs can be considered, and efficiency of a system in terms of labour inputs, in terms of nutrient utilisation or in monetary terms may look very different. For different purposes and depending on data availability, different definitions and operationalisations were chosen in different analyses within the MIXED project (see D6.1, p.16). As mixedness aims at the closing of nutrient cycles, efficiency in terms of nutrients is perhaps the central concept for the MIXED project as a whole; efficiency in terms of labour has shown to be another key issue (see below).

2.2 Farm-level MiFAS – resilience, sustainability and efficiency

Different analyses in the MIXED project have found evidence that MiFAS at the farm level can be highly resilient, sustainable and, under the right conditions, efficient and profitable. The context, frames of comparison and specific execution of the systems are, however, crucial for realising these potentials, and different systems perform differently regarding the various measures of interest. This section aims to provide an overview of important aspects that should be considered regarding MiFAS at farm scale, details however can be learned from the individual deliverables within the MIXED project.

Mixed farming and agroforestry systems can have significant **sustainability** advantages. Integration within MiFAS can lead to better resource utilization and land-use efficiency compared to specialised systems, as is known from the literature (Low et al. 2023). Well implemented and managed MiFAS that realise the potentials for, among other things, more efficient use of land or nutrients, are advantageous in terms of carbon footprint and nitrogen run-off, as life-cycle analyses demonstrate. These advantages only hold true, however, if more mixed farming does not bring about more livestock in a system (Low et al. 2023).

Modelling of the farm scale impacts of different scenarios of mixed system adoption in D5.4 demonstrates that, while more mixedness can bring about decreases in emissions (carbon footprint, terrestrial acidification, and freshwater eutrophication), integration of trees and organic farming practices often do better than just an integration of cropping and animal husbandry. This analysis also points to the importance of choosing the right system for the natural conditions, as it shows that enforcing mixedness in a way that leads to a more arable farming on less productive soils would yield worse results in terms of not only efficiency, but also emissions. Results at the landscape scale (D3.3) point in the same direction: Grassland, usually on soils or in climatic conditions not suitable for arable farming, should generally not be made more mixed at the cost of ploughing it. Both studies also

highlight that intensive livestock systems will remain problematic; for effective improvements in sustainability, animal numbers need to be reduced to avoid nutrient excesses and subsequent losses (D5.4).

Further sustainability advantages include effects such as improved conditions for pollinators and other beneficial fauna, allowing a reduction of pesticide use, agroforestry alleviating soil erosion and improving soil retention etc. In addition to being described in the literature (analysed and summarised by Low et al., 2023), such benefits are exemplified in innovation studies (D2.4) in MIXED.

Within farm-level analysis by means of data envelopment analysis of FADN data, MiFAS were found to be, on average, more **resilient** than specialised farms, and this stems from higher adaptability and transformability, whereas the third dimension of resilience in the analysis, robustness, was lower for MiFAS. A regression analysis reveals a U-shaped relationship between resilience and efficiency, thus there appear to be trade-offs at lower levels and synergies at higher levels of efficiency (D6.2, p. 16, 27). Efficiency, for this analysis, was measured in the long term. As a substantive explanation, it is therefore suggested that resilience helps in maintaining efficiency over the long term (D6.2, p. 22).

The broad literature review on MiFAS with particular focus on implications for food value chains has shown that MiFAS can be more resilient against market and price risks such as price volatility for inputs and outputs. The literature review also points to certain MiFAS having greater resilience to climate change, e.g. due to trees providing shade and animals removing combustible materials, thus preventing wildfires (Low et al. 2023). High dependence on human labour can be a liability in terms of resilience, especially where demands for labour are highly seasonal, such as in the systems involving fruit or seasonal breeding livestock. This may be exacerbated by uncertainties resulting from increasing extreme weather events (D5.2, D4.3).

In principle, the integration between sub-systems, which is the cause of a large part of the sustainability advantages of MFS, also presents potential for savings in variable costs. In terms of profitability, synergies (or economies of scope) are, however, often insufficient to make up for a disadvantage in terms of economies of scale compared to specialised farms. Higher labour needs of MFS are a main cause their lower **efficiency** (Low et al. 2023). In a Europe-wide analysis of farm-level FADN data by means of data envelopment analysis, MiFAS were also overall found to be less efficient (as a relation of inputs, including labour and material inputs, to outputs), but results vary based on environmental zones. There are highly efficient mixed farms in the dataset, which points to highly efficient MiFAS being possible (D6.2).

Efficiency purely in terms of nutrient use can potentially be better in MiFAS, e.g. as manure is used efficiently as fertiliser rather than applied in the largest allowable amounts; results from the MIXED project are, however, overall not clear cut, in that specialised systems can be highly efficient in nutrient use due to high expertise (D5.4 and D6.2), but organic systems tend to excel in nutrient efficiency (D5.4) and overall, intensive livestock is detrimental in any system, although its impacts can be mitigated to varying degrees (Low et al. 2023, D4.5, D5.1).

Overall, efficiency is the one aspect that is often a challenge for farms with mixed systems (Low et al. 2023), but this does not apply in all cases and the salience of this factor and whether it remains an issue at the level of farm economics is contingent on the priorities in support policy. In cases where systems excel in other aspects but, under current conditions, lack profitability, an altered reward/incentive structure and remuneration of potential losses to make the systems economically viable for farmers can be worthwhile and is a matter of trade-offs that should be holistically considered.

Specialised farms tend to benefit more from economies of scale, compared to farm-level MiFAS. Low et al. (2023) have, however, shown that, while MFS can more efficiently use resources such as land and nutrients, as is frequently stated in the literature, the synergies of integrating arable and

livestock farming in one farm tend to not economically make up for the disadvantage in terms of economies of scale: On farms that switched to a mixed crop-livestock system, as the size of each system typically decreased, and in the case of livestock farms diversifying into more arable farming, there was a reduction in the, comparatively higher, revenue from livestock farming. One approach to the question of efficiency is mixedness at the landscape scale, much of the results on WP 6 point to this; results are summarised in 2.3.

Examples from the project

In general, it can be assumed that the efficiency and resilience of **agroforestry systems (AFS)** vary as much as the systems themselves. Therefore, it is not practical to draw general conclusions, but rather to do so on a case-by-case basis.

The discussions of the network partners during the back casting workshops (WP1), network workshops and result mining workshops (both WP6) partly developed around the (improved) efficiency and resilience of AFS. However, especially as some of the AFS are only at the experimental stage, these were rather assumptions and goals than fact-based observations (D1.1):

- In the context of Austria including the Austrian agroforestry network (apple-hens), there is a shift towards specialization leading to increased efficiency. However, Knickel et al. (2018) postulated that this comes with the risk of a decrease in farm resilience. In general, mixed farming operations, reconnecting livestock and cropping activities were assumed as more resilient and with better chances to cope with ecological challenges (D1.1). However, the introduction of livestock grazing underneath plantation-like orchards like with the apple-hens, relies on handpicking, which increases labour demand, and making it a high-cost system.
- In the case of the French agroforestry network, the results of the back casting workshop mentioned a reduction in the consumption of cereals during the period when the trees are producing acorns, which offer a high level of protein and mineral elements. While pigs benefit from the shade of the trees, they can also cause damage (bark, root damage, etc.) and leave the ground bare and prone to erosion (BC-WS FR1). This illustrates the delicate balance between trees and livestock density.
- Farmers in the Portuguese network mentioned that the Montado, as an old traditional AFS with scattered oak trees and extensive livestock production, is now vulnerable to climate change and soil degradation. Therefore, in this network, the approach is to adjust the traditionally mixed system through increasing its diversity, resp. modifying the mixedness of the system (RM-WS WP2), to ensure its economic viability and environmental sustainability (D1.1), and thus its resilience.

Some project results of MIXED allowed for the development of specific arguments regarding the efficiency and resilience of AFS:

- The results of the Danish case indicated that the agroforestry pig farm exhibited greater resilience and efficiency, particularly in terms of nitrogen leaching. Significant variables for consideration included livestock stocking density and planting density of the trees (RM-WS WP2).
- A comparative analysis of apple-hen farms with more intensive egg production indicates a lesser carbon footprint for the eggs derived from the AFS. This land use is presumed to be more efficient in terms of area, feed use, nitrogen leaching – and provides shade and shelter. While additional benefits remain to be identified, it is plausible that reduced disease pressure and fertilisation in the fruit production may also be observed (RM-WS WP4).

In the vast diversity of AFS, efficiency and resilience are still system dependent. In the case of the Swiss network, high-stem fruit trees with livestock grazing underneath, investigations revealed that extreme weather events, such as late frost, might have a significant impact on the quantity of apples

collected at designated locations. Consequently, these value chains may be susceptible to external shocks (RM-WS WP6, Low et al. 2023). However, it seems reasonable to conclude that this vulnerability is associated with fruit cultivation in general and is not specific to agroforestry utilisation.

While there is a considerable amount of both theoretical and practical evidence that suggests an increased efficiency and resilience of AFS, some questions remain to be answered. While it can be reasonably argued that AFS positively contribute to environmental aspects and are vastly acknowledged as sustainable land use practices, current research focuses on their potential for climate change mitigation and adaptation, for example, through the creation of carbon sinks.

- MIXED results show that, in LCA, the effects of AFS on other environmental aspects, such as biodiversity, water, soil and pollination, remain only superficially known (Quevedo-Cascante et al. 2023). Nevertheless, all these aspects might have an impact on the efficiency and resilience of the systems in question.
- In contrast to the more immediate assessment of arable land use on a year-by-year basis, AFS necessitate longer-term observation periods, e.g. with several years typically elapsing from planting to the initial harvest. This longevity of AFS poses challenges in predicting their environmental, management, economic and other impacts, including efficiency and resilience (RM-WS WP5, Lefort et al., forthcoming). This is particularly relevant when examining newly planted systems.
- An assessment of efficiency and resilience is also contingent upon economies of scale. This became evident in the case of the Polish network, which represents a single, large-scale agricultural entity. In this instance, while the AFS has been shown to provide beneficial effects, such as reducing pests, increasing beneficial insects, increasing soil moisture, and increasing biological activity (D2.4, see 2.4), it remained unclear how this translates into increased resilience and efficiency at farm scale (RM-WS WP2).

D1.1 mentioned a decline in the numbers of **crop-livestock systems** at farm level, e.g. in Austria, France and Scotland. This applies in particular to traditional integrated crop-livestock systems, which are now mostly concentrated in less favoured areas such as upland or mountainous regions, even though 'traditional crop-livestock systems enable self-sufficiency and autonomy by producing all the necessary inputs to production' (D1.1, p. 13).

- As an example, in Scotland, traditional mixed systems typically include cereals, beef and sheep. However, especially in the most productive arable areas, very few arable farmers remain with livestock.
- Similarly, in the northern parts of the Netherlands, most farms specialise in either arable crops or livestock, resulting in low to moderate resilience capacities (Spiegel et al. 2022). According to this study, the current policy framework promotes robustness and tends to neglect transformability; hence, there is a high capacity to maintain the status quo and, conversely, a low capacity for transformation. Spiegel et al. (2022) identified circular agriculture and improved soil management, two aspects typical of MiFAS, as potential future strategies for the region. Another avenue which farmers have been successfully exploring for several years is cooperation, including land exchange, across farms (also see 2.3).

In the back casting workshops, the potential risk of disease and the multitude of regulations associated with the introduction of livestock, especially on arable land, was one of the main perceptions regarding the reintroduction of crop-livestock systems (D1.1).

MIXED project results partly allowed are more precise view on some of the crop-livestock systems under study.

- The analysis of the FADN data, which includes economic mixedness of farms but not agroforestry, suggested that in terms of the coping mechanisms of MiFAS for extreme weather

events, a change from a specialised livestock farm to a mixed crop-livestock farm could have a negative impact in this respect (RM-WS WP4).

- Low et al. (2023) noted the importance of synergies between farming enterprises, particularly in terms of the provision of public goods and reduced dependence on external inputs. They also identified greater resilience to production and price risks, and improved land use efficiency. These benefits are also amplified by inter-farm cooperation and territorial connectivity (Low et al. 2023, also see 2.3).
- D5.4 found that the re-integration of cropping and livestock systems showed some potential to improve environmental indicators, especially when underutilised resources are used as inputs to reduce external inputs. However, the straight substitution of externally sourced concentrate feeds for on-farm produced feeds within intensive livestock systems is unlikely to solve the main issue of nutrient excesses. More balanced systems such as organic farms had high nutrient use efficiency, reduced external reliance on inputs, similar or lower product environmental footprints, as well as potentially improved economic performance due to price premia.

2.3 Landscape level mixed farming – resilience, sustainability and efficiency

The landscape perspective at a regional (not necessarily administrative) scale is crucial for understanding mixed agricultural and agroforestry systems. This scale allows for the examination of how diverse land uses, such as crop fields, pastures, forests, and wetlands, interact and influence each other within a broader context, also beyond farm holding boundaries.

Mixedness at a territorial scale can result from mixed farms or a mix of specialised farms. Heterogeneity can and should be included in a region under consideration, be it for analytical or practical purposes, as in the MIXED network FR2 of crop farmers and livestock farmers in the Ariège region in south-western France. The foundation of the synergies here are the differences between the higher altitude pasturelands and lower-lying farmland, both of which can be used optimally, and traditionally, in animal husbandry and arable farming, respectively. On the other hand, the Montado of the southern Iberian Peninsula is a mixed landscape (also studied in the MIXED project, e.g. D1.1, D2.4) that is the result of one single agroforestry practice largely defining the whole landscape. While very different, both cases exemplify ideal usage of natural conditions through mixedness. In a similar vein, findings of a study that modelled land use reallocation for England and Wales demonstrate that mixedness and optimum land use go hand in hand, as they highlight potentials ‘to simultaneously increase production and reduce nitrogen losses, while also increasing crop diversity at farm and regional level’ (D6.3, p. 28).

The distributions and make-up of mixed landscape varies widely over different environmental zones (see D3.3, 6.3). Across Europe, mixed landscapes tend contain more mixed farms, but even in mixed landscapes, specialised farms are most prevalent (D6.3). Landscape level mixedness as a result of interactions of specialised farms allows for the efficiency in terms of economies of scale and focused expertise of specialised farms (D6.2), while increasing circularity, ideally more efficient resource use etc. in a region.

Low et al. (2023) note the importance of synergies that can be realised by cooperation between farming enterprises and further local interactions, particularly in terms of the provision of public goods and reduced dependence on external inputs. They also identify greater resilience to production and price risks, and improved land use efficiency (p. 9). It is, furthermore, very plausible to assume that many resilience and sustainability benefits of mixed farms (see above as well as Low et al. 2023, D6.2) extend to the landscape scale. Diversity and circularity are taken to result in resilience in D6.3 (study 2): ‘We refer to mixed agricultural landscapes as those characterised by greater circularity

and diversity and therefore are more adept at handling climate change challenges' (D6.3, p. 5, also see p. 2). With nitrogen balance, a measure of sustainability was also built into the operationalisation of landscape-level mixedness here (D6.3, p. 6).

As far as these premises hold true, mixedness at the landscape level allows for the efficiency of specialised farming while improving resilience. The expected greater circularity in mixed landscapes is empirically confirmed in D3.3. Therein lays great potential for improvements at little cost – what needs to be overcome to establish more cooperation appear to largely be trust and coordination issues (see 3, also D6.3 on cost-effective ways to achieve more mixedness). As more diversity and circularity at regional or local level are urgently needed is most obvious in specialisation tendencies of whole regions, e.g. the livestock clusters of northern central Europe. To counteract the substantial negative externalities in such cases, more mixedness at the landscape level is a promising approach – within the constraints of farming and agroforestry practices appropriate for the local conditions (see D3.3).

Examples from the project

Six networks in the MIXED project explore different models of collaboration: A network in France (FR2) focused on livestock-crop integration, with farmers exchanging grazing land and manure to improve soil health. In Germany, a network (DE1) works on peatland conservation through extensive, low-input farming. Nutrient recycling, using manure and digestate exchanges to close nutrient cycles, is the objective of a network in Denmark (DK2). Two networks of farmers in Scotland tested livestock reintegration into arable systems, with sheep winter grazing to enhance soil fertility and use an additional source of high-quality feed (UK2), grazing cattle and fodder exchange within a network of beef suckler herds and arable farmers (UK1). A network of arable and dairy farmers on peat and sandy land in the Netherlands has been practicing land and manure exchange (NL).

The undertakings of the networks were accompanied by researchers of the MIXED project and subjected to life-cycle analyses, published in D5.1, excluding the network in the Netherlands, which was part of an analysis in which the value chain network was studied (D4.3). The winter grazing practices of one Scottish network (UK2) were also the subject of an innovation study (D2.4). Further information on the networks is summarised in D2.1 and D5.6, which are concerned with the testing of a serious game designed to help farmers represent, analyse and discuss their farming systems at the landscape scale (the development of the serious game is documented in D5.3 and D5.6, also see Ryschawy et al. 2022).

The Dutch network (NL), in the northeast Veenkoloniën region with poor soils, consists of specialised dairy and arable farmers who make **their crop rotations more extensive by exchanging land**. As farming in this region is not very profitable, the savings in inputs this exchange brings about are especially important. It was also expected to improve soils and prevent pest problems due to tight crop rotations. This case of cooperation highlights the importance of interpersonal relations for cooperation, as 'this cooperation does not rely on any formal regulations and hence requires very tight interactions and trust among farmers' (Spiegel et al. 2022, p. 209).

The networks in Scotland explored **sheep (UK2) and cattle (UK1) grazing cover crops, crop residues or winter cereals**. For arable farmers, allowing livestock to graze crop residues and cover crops improved soil fertility and reduced fertiliser costs and for livestock farmers, winter grazing lowered feed expenses. It was mentioned that grazing winter cereals may be more resilient and efficient than grazing cover crops. However, this depends heavily on context specifics. For example: If the farmer does not know the amount of biomass to expect, they might decide not to contact a shepherd to graze the fields, as they might not be able to provide enough feed. On the other hand, a major advantage is that winter cereals are more flexible than cover crops. They are not tied to specific dates (administrative) and management steps (e.g. spring sowing) (RM-WS WP2, RM-WS WP4).

Nitrogen utilisation rates were among the most balanced in the analysis (D5.1). French farmers from Ariège visited the Scottish network during the MIXED project and were quickly convinced to implement similar practices.

In the network in the Ariège region in South-Western France (FR2), seven farms – including arable, livestock, and mixed operations – **cooperated to exchange fodder and manure**. The livestock farms are generally rather extensive and located at higher altitudes than the crop farms, a key form of collaboration was winter grazing on arable farms, where sheep and cattle fed on cover crops, reducing the need for external feed while naturally fertilising the soil.

Danish farms (DK2) focused on reducing nutrient excesses, which affect the shallow and nutrient vulnerable waters of the Limfjord, through exchange between biogas production and farms, helping to close nutrient cycles and reduce dependence on synthetic fertilisers. Due to the intensity of some livestock farms in the network, the efforts proved insufficient to bring emissions down to healthy levels (D5.1).

Across these networks, cooperation enabled better nutrient management, cost savings, and environmental benefits. Crop-livestock integration appears particularly promising, helping to reduce fertiliser and feed dependence. Biogas and nutrient exchanges can improve efficiency, yet intensive systems still faced high nitrogen losses. Meanwhile, conservation farming on peatland has clear environmental benefits but required financial support to be viable.

Overall, these networks show that collaboration in farming can lead to more sustainable and resilient systems, but successful implementation depends on mutually beneficial agreements, effective management, and financial viability. That the presence of MIXED teams in several cases helped facilitate cooperation highlights that aid with coordination may generally be needed to overcome initial hurdles toward more landscape-level mixedness (this results in policy recommendations in section 4.3).

2.4 Case studies on other types of MiFAS

Three networks covered in MIXED – namely Rewetting of arable land (Germany), Integrated large farm (Poland) and small farms & agritourism (Romania) – do not fall into any of the types of MiFAS described above. Still, they provide relevant insights into specific types of mixed farming and agro-forestry systems.

2.4.1 Rewetting of arable land – ArGe Donaumoos, Germany

The ArGe Donaumoos (Network DE1) is landscape conservation association located in Bavaria, Germany and manages a landscape area of about 10.000 ha (with 2200 ha of peatland, and 2700 ha of hillside and floodplain forest). Facilitating the development of a close partnership between agriculture and nature conservation, their focus is on preserving and developing an open, ecologically intact wetland landscape, whereas the management of the peatland is based on a compatible land use for nature conservation and climate change protection.

Peatlands are generally wet to moist and high in carbon. Draining such soils, e.g., for agricultural use, releases this carbon mainly as carbon dioxide (CO₂). In 2022, drained peat soils in Germany, primarily used for agriculture, emitted around 43 Mio. t of CO₂-equivalents. This is equal to around 80 per cent of the total greenhouse gas emissions from German peatlands (Umweltbundesamt 2024, BC-WS DE1).

Peat soils must be rewetted or maintained in a wet state, with water levels no more than 20 cm below the surface, to preserve the soil and their ability to sequester carbon. Rewetting generally exceeds the size of existing fields and significantly reduces the potential for agricultural use. This network is seen as a 'case study' since its emphasis is on peatland protection and habitat restoration rather

than maximising yields and economic profits. Hence, despite the clear benefits for climate change mitigation, wet farming comes with many challenges.

Regarding these specific challenges, it was mentioned that ‘many [farmers] cannot easily adapt their operational structures and processes to [wet] agriculture. [They] lack the financial leeway and the necessary expertise and support’ (BC-WS DE1). In this case, the lack of knowledge and capacity building among farmers, advisors and policymakers focused on the understanding and practicing of paludiculture techniques. Farmers also identified the lack in value creation as a bottleneck, if they produce products with costs that are typically higher than the alternatives from specialised farming systems. Also, the provision of public goods is rarely remunerated, and the administrative burden increases due to the complexity of the land use system (BC-WS DE1, D1.1).

MIXED project results indicated that cooperation among farms was essential in coordinating the rewetting process as well as water and nutrient management. By prioritising organic fertilization and avoiding deep tillage, these farms significantly reduced nitrogen losses and carbon emissions (D5.1). However, despite these environmental benefits, D5.1 states that ‘even under protective management nutrient rich peatlands can emit high levels of GHG’ (D5.1, p. 30), and that the forage from rewetted land has a high emission factor, resulting in unfavourable carbon footprints of livestock products. In addition, economic sustainability remained a challenge. With low productivity and market competitiveness, farms relied on subsidies to maintain economic viability. Overall, the results indicated that conservation farming as practiced in this network can be effective but requires cooperation, as well as long-term financial support to be economically viable.

2.4.2 Integrated large farm – FSK Juchowo, Poland

The Stanisław Karłowski Foundation FSK Juchowo in north-west Poland is a diversified farm that integrates education, sociotherapy, scientific research, and nature conservation, resulting in a near-circular model with multiple revenue streams. The farm practices biodynamic agriculture across 1,900 hectares, focusing on dairy cattle, animal fodder, cereals, root crops, vegetables, and fruit (D1.1)

Juchowo thus represents mixedness at the farm level, but as a large integrated farm, also sees effects at a landscape level, and integrates aspects of agroforestry. The soil is naturally rather poor and sandy and additionally has been degraded by unsustainable use in the past; tree lines and hedges have been planted to act as wind brakes in the face of increasing winds due to climate change and thus help prevent soil erosion, to enhance biodiversity, and provide shade for the farm’s cattle. The benefits of this practice were evaluated in the MIXED project and published in D2.4. In proximity to the tree rows, less pests were found, which is attributed to the improved habitat for beneficial fauna that preys on pests. Pollination, soil moisture and microbial activity, as well as soil carbon and nitrogen content were found improved in the proximity of trees; soil temperatures were found to be lower. The trees are also thought to reduce wind speeds, thereby reducing evapotranspiration and wind erosion. Crop yields were often found to be higher near trees, although certain crops yielded less in proximity to old trees.

The farm is fully self-sufficient for fertilisers and imports little nitrogen in livestock feed. The farm is thus highly efficient in terms of nutrients, and its sustainability and resilience benefit from saving on their transportation and independence from market developments.

The farm’s performance in nutrient, economic, GHG and environmental terms has been assessed in D5.1. Based on the assumptions in these models, Juchowo is ‘exporting more nitrogen in products than it imports [...] with a risk of mining the farm’s nitrogen reserves.’ Nutrient inputs are very low per area, but per livestock unit are not quite as low as on comparable farms analysed in D5.1. The low productivity per ha, due to the poor soils, explains the difference between the two nutrient input

measures. For the same reason, GHG emissions per area are very low, but less so in relation to nitrogen in exported products.

The livestock side of the farm is unprofitable by itself, but the earnings with crops outweigh these losses (D5.1), leading to a positive net margin, and the animals provide necessary manure for the crops. The low dependence on market inputs is beneficial from both efficiency and resilience points of view. The farm however faces challenges in obtaining good prices for its products, and in dealing with the volatility of the organic food market. A further challenge is in finding and qualifying labour and managing the different concurrent demands for technical and human resources on the farm (D5.2). The efficiency in terms of labour inputs would require special considerations as the farm, with a total of 150 employees, is integrated with a sociotherapy operation, including 50 employees and 25 supervisors in a sheltered workshop.

2.4.3 Small farms & agritourism – LAG Tinutul Posadelor, Romania

The Romanian case study focuses on the LAG Tinutul Posadelor region, a mountainous area with 28,000 small farms, most under 5 hectares. Integrating trees and shrubs with crops and livestock is still common on these small Romanian farms. The MIXED project collaborates with eight smallholder farmers in this area who practice diverse mixed systems involving crops, livestock, natural pastures, orchards, and agritourism. The goals include increasing awareness of mixed farming, diversifying activities, integrating local forests, enhancing cooperation and sharing experience among farmers as well as improving integration into local supply chains for better profitability.

The mixed small farms have, by their continued existence, demonstrated a degree of resilience. Their diversity and limited reliance on external inputs, banks, and specialised markets gives them flexibility in production and sales. On pure efficiency, however, they cannot compete with large, specialised farms, which dominate the plains in Romania, and thus small farms have largely been reduced to mountainous areas. Even there, however, there is a trend towards larger farms and the mixed small farms are under economic pressure. They often are not profitable enough to be able to afford the investments that would be needed to grow and become more efficient. Lacking regional storage facilities and thus concentration of supply, they also have limited access to value chains that are geared to large producers. The formation of producer organisations and regional marketing of the products of the farms as one possible avenue to address these problems was discussed in a field workshop in the MIXED project. Other possibilities to generate revenue that are being explored include agritourism and direct marketing of farm produce.

For the LCA conducted and described in D5.1, a representative farm for the region was created based on the available data. These farms typically have a small number but high stocking density of livestock and various fruit trees on pastures or in orchards.

The modelled farm efficiently manages nitrogen by importing only a small amount of feed to supplement grassland forage for its herd. Livestock is the primary product exported. However, with a nitrogen use efficiency exceeding 100 %, there is a risk of nitrogen depletion in the soil, which could lead to reduced productivity in the long term. Greenhouse gas emissions are relatively high for a low-input system, primarily due to the high stocking density of dairy cattle. Including organic carbon estimates could potentially offset up to 5 % of these emissions.

The model farm shows a negative partial net margin due to high costs associated with livestock production. However, its crop production is profitable.'

3 Challenges for a transition to MiFAS

We can distinguish between general challenges to MiFAS management that hinder broader adoption, and implementation-specific challenges that must be overcome for wider use but will not persist after the transition. The latter include cultural shifts, needs for investments, systemic changes, and incentives for the implementation of MiFAS. Structures in terms of value chains as well as farming are often geared towards large-scale monoculture and the related large plots, numbers of animals, and delivered quantities in inputs and outputs. These are deeply entrenched paths, leaving them is often difficult and costly. Due to such path dependencies, some degree of inertia must often be overcome, e.g. to establish new value chains, where initially, transaction costs are higher and economies of scale lacking, compared to established systems, or self-sustaining phenomena such as peer advice not yet viable. Even purely technical issues such as the availability of specialised machinery highly depend on a minimum demand. Once critical thresholds are reached, however, the need for external help in overcoming these challenges can be expected to decline. Policy recommendations formulated to address challenges of this category are collected in 4.5.2.

Challenges to the general management of MiFAS will remain past such a transition phase and can often be thought of as a matter of conflicting goals at farm and societal levels. Farm level economic goals in the short and long term may be in conflict, e.g. immediate productivity and long-term soil fertility. Individual and collective (public goods) goals also need to be constantly balanced. For instance, to reap benefits in terms of environmental and social sustainability and resilience, it may be necessary to accept the need for higher labour inputs and adjust compensation to induce farms to adopt these currently economically unviable systems. Such challenges of conflicting goals are not unique to the wider adoption of MiFAS but rather are constantly navigated in agriculture and agricultural policy. Policy recommendations to aid the ongoing management of MiFAS are to be found in 4.5.3.

Most transition challenges have in common that they depend upon systemic changes that can only be brought about by fundamentally re-shaped priorities in agricultural policy to transform the agri-food system to meet agreed upon goals and commitments and follow the principle *public money for public goods* (see 4.5.1 for recommendations to address the systemic issues that inhibit MiFAS adoption).

The challenges that stand in the way of a transition to more MiFAS were identified in a series of 13 workshops in all 10 countries and can be grouped into technical issues, knowledge and skills, profitability, supply chain, regulation, public funding, and cultural and societal challenges as described in detail in D1.1. While the back casting workshops identified issues that are not specific to MiFAS, but are also relevant to agriculture in general, these were not central to the MIXED project, where the policy focus was on challenges specific to MiFAS. In summary, there are still wide-ranging gaps and challenges that need to be addressed to create a policy environment more conducive to MiFAS.

Technical challenges that stand in the way of a wider adoption of MiFAS for different systems in different context are diverse. They range from different needs in machinery to sanitary questions and needs for more research on optimal system implementation and management. Many of the challenges that the MIXED networks worked on in the field workshops (WP1) can be categorised as technical challenges.

Knowledge and skills challenges are manifold. Practical research is needed as the requirements for MiFAS run counter to the general trend towards more specialisation, which also manifests in the training and advisory systems, and is reinforced by advice from input providers like fertiliser and pesticide companies. MiFAS require specialist knowledge of their implementation and management and their impact on ecosystems. This includes, for example, knowledge of a wide range of agricultural crops, arable farming and animal husbandry. Effective policy formulation requires consolidated

knowledge about the conditions under which public goods provision from MiFAS is optimal as well as about losses or incurred costs that may need to be compensated.

Many rural areas already face shortages of labour (BC-WS PL). As the general trend has been toward specialisation in agriculture, knowledge and skills in the breadth needed for mixed systems get harder to come by and are often also lacking among the farmers. For instance, forestry skills are relatively rare among farmers and the agricultural workforce (BC-WS UK) but needed for agroforestry. This issue however is not confined to more unusual systems, it presents already as a divide between animal husbandry and arable farming skills (BC-WS UK).

Challenges in the way of a transition to more MiFAS from a farm business perspective revolve around **profitability**, which is contingent upon the subsidy regime as well as the valuation of farm products and the positioning in the respective value chains (see below). Profitability takes a crucial position among the challenges in the transition, as it is a necessary condition to wider adoption. The products and public goods that MiFAS can provide are often not adequately remunerated on the market or through support measures (see below). In many cases, transitioning to more mixed farming requires significant investments. Acquiring new machinery and adapting production methods or even planting trees is costly, and a barrier especially in the face of (demand, land tenure, climate, or regulatory) uncertainties. Beside the needed certainty for planning and access to financing, farmers often lack financial flexibility and may require specialised counselling.

MiFAS are often **labour** intensive, as they benefit less from mechanisation and economies of scale. D5.2 identified difficulties of finding qualified labour, in addition to challenges of seasonal labour peaks increased in mixed systems. The insight that labour-related issues are a central obstacle to the more widespread adoption of MiFAS (D1.1) is well known (EIP-Agri Service Point 2017). Labour is often a very significant cost factor in the current system that mainly subsidises area. Thus, efficiency in terms of labour is often an important factor for the feasibility of systems, which may not be offset by savings from synergies through mixedness (Low et al. 2023, p. 10).

MiFAS often face difficulty fitting in existing commodity **value chains** that are geared toward larger amounts of agricultural goods with less regard to their origin and method of production. The typical long and complex supply chains do seldomly accommodate multiple products from a single farm, incurring increased transaction costs. Commonly there is a lack of local processing, storage and marketing channels and facilities, which however, are needed for integration in, ideally, shorter and more localised supply chains. Where local processing facilities, especially for perishable products, and slaughterhouses are unavailable, farmers may be unable to keep or establish the respective production systems. More generally, local processing, storage and marketing offer potentials for keeping a greater value added for the farmers, to communicate MiFAS benefits to consumers and to secure higher producer prices. Cooperation between farms can help smaller farms to enjoy these benefits. Low et al. (2023) and D4.3 offer a more detailed view on value chains in the MIXED project.

Regulatory and administrative challenges revolve around the fact that the framework on EU and national levels was widely considered deficient in that it tends to lack specificity for MiFAS and encourages specialisation. As a direct consequence of the legal conditions thus created, farmers with MiFAS risk losing subsidies in many possible scenarios where MiFAS don't fit into prescribed categories. Agricultural and forestry policies and administrative domains remain largely separate. This adds to the already complex bureaucratic and administrative burdens for those trying to integrate different practices and may even lead farmers to rule out the possibility of a mixed system altogether. Especially the rigid separation of land uses for agriculture and forestry can be an obstacle for agroforestry. The division between animal husbandry and plant production into distinct regulatory domains creates challenges for other mixed farming systems (D1.1). Further issues in specific cases may stand in the way of suitable MiFAS include for example that forest products currently cannot receive organic status under Regulation (EU) 2018/848, resulting in constrained marketing of such

products. Uncertainty about regulatory or funding policy changes as well as about other developments, such as the climate and markets, is an obstacle for the required longer-term commitments in conjunction with MiFAS (D1.1). Moreover, the narrow focus on climate change as a main aspect of sustainability may raise questions about how to value other ecosystem services and public goods (Quevedo-Cascante et al. 2023).

MiFAS often struggle to secure the financial backing necessary to thrive, as their unique needs are frequently not considered by policymakers, resulting in a lack of **public funding**. The CAP and its implementation in the member states disproportionately support intensive conventional production over sustainable practices, including mixed systems, and have shown low effectiveness in promoting pro-environmental EU objectives (European Court of Auditors 2024; European Environmental Board and BirdLife Europe 2022). It is in this context that many challenges to a wider adoption of MiFAS must be understood. Economic feasibility in this system largely rests on the area-based payments of the CAP and economies of scale; non-market outputs that benefit the public have been scarcely remunerated. Other inputs, including the pre-requisite knowledge and labour, more of which is often needed in MiFAS, have not received enough support. These challenges thus reflect those mentioned above as farm business challenges. MiFAS deliver a complex range of public goods that are thus not currently valued. If these benefits are wanted, public funding must remunerate these non-market outputs, cover additional costs or incurred losses that cannot be recouped on the markets, and thus correct the incentive structure for farmers. There is a pressing need to measure and recognise these public goods to offset the productivity losses often associated with MiFAS, ensuring that farmers can achieve a sustainable livelihood.

Societal and cultural obstacles that hinder the wider adoption of MiFAS exist in the farming and related communities and in society. While farmers are generally aware of mixed farming practices, at least traditional ones in their region, they may consider them backward and outdated, or be sceptical of change without certainty of profitability. A lack of awareness and understanding of mixed farming system approaches and their benefits in terms of public goods, as a pre-requisite to appreciation and willingness to remunerate these services, is still pervasive among the public as well as among policymakers and administrators. Collaboration among farmers brings about transaction costs and requires trust that is often lacking, making it challenging to establish and maintain collaborative MiFAS without the presence of external facilitation. Similar issues relate to the establishment of new supply chains and peer networks for advice. A key challenge identified is the lack of motivation or incentive (see above) for farmers to transition from specialised systems to MiFAS. This challenge is tied to the declining appeal of farming as a career and the need for generational change to shift established practices (D1.1, EIP-Agri Service Point 2017). Gender issues also contribute, particularly concerning labour shortages and the need to address the specific needs of both men and women in the agricultural workforce to ensure long-term solutions. Societal pressures for public goods, like landscape maintenance, pose another challenge, as the public often lacks understanding of farming's broader contributions, especially regarding MiFAS, where clear production principles are less defined compared to e.g. certified organic farming.

4 Policy Brief

European agriculture is at a crossroad, facing mounting pressures from climate change, biodiversity loss, economic uncertainties, and shifting societal expectations. The ongoing transformation of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) of the European Union aims to address these challenges by promoting greater sustainability, resilience, and competitiveness in the farming sector. Achieving these goals requires an integrated, science-based, and collaborative approach that balances economic viability with environmental and social responsibility. In this approach, farmers must play a central and co-decisive role to be equal partners in the transformation.

The MIXED project explored the benefits of mixed farming and agroforestry systems (MiFAS) to climate, environment and society and aimed at further developing such systems. MiFAS integrate crop, forestry, and livestock production within a field, farm, or landscape to optimise resource use through collaboration and diversification. This approach enhances sustainability by improving resource utilisation and land use efficiency compared to specialised systems. MiFAS also increase farm resilience and promote a circular use of resources, contributing to the EU's agricultural sustainability goals.

The following **policy recommendations** build on these insights, providing practical pathways to align EU agricultural policy with the urgent need for sustainable and resilient food systems. By integrating these approaches, the CAP and its implementations in the Member States can evolve into a more adaptive and forward-looking framework, ensuring that European agriculture thrives in the face of future challenges. Although partners and networks in Switzerland and the United Kingdom are part of the project and many considerations may apply to non-EU contexts, the following policy recommendations address specifically the agricultural policy regime in the EU and target policymakers, agricultural associations, and environmental organizations. It is imperative that specificities at sub-national levels be considered. Consequently, general policy recommendations are provided that aim to address common challenges and opportunities across Europe, but full use should be made of subsidiarity in implementation; national, regional and local legislators and administrations should exercise their expertise, fine-tune instruments and set priorities.

The **Strategic Dialogue on the Future of EU Agriculture** (EC 2024) represents a major milestone in the transition towards more sustainability, resilience, and competitiveness in the farming sector. Bringing together key stakeholders, it has fostered a broad consensus on the need for a CAP that better supports farmers, enhances sustainability, and strengthens rural communities. Its findings highlight the importance of diversified farming models, including MiFAS, to improve resource efficiency, ecosystem resilience, and economic stability. The *Strategic Dialogue* underscores the urgent need for more resilient, efficient, and sustainable agricultural and agroforestry systems in response to climate change, biodiversity loss, and environmental degradation. Moreover, it also highlights the necessity of scaling up adaptation measures at both farm and landscape levels to mitigate climate risks and enhance long-term sustainability (EC 2024 p. 75). It also emphasises that without adaptation, farming in some regions could become unsustainable due to climate-induced challenges and calls for systematic support to help farmers implement resilient agricultural systems while maintaining economic viability. The report indicates a need for a more fundamental shift 'away from current non-degressive area-based payments towards an effective income support approach', amongst others for mixed farms (EC 2024, p. 43).

MIXED's findings largely echo the *Strategic Dialogue's* recommendations. For example, the need for substantial change in agricultural policy is reflected in the finding that current difficulties in internalising the environmental and social value-added by MiFAS have a negative impact on their economic sustainability (Low et al. 2023). The economic competitiveness of MiFAS could therefore look very different in a prospective system that internalises more of the effects of agriculture than the current regime. The consequences of current livestock numbers point to a further need for change in food system policies, as a reduction in livestock intensity implies a societal shift towards a more plant-based diet (D5.4). In the absence of a wider transformation of the food and agriculture system, the recommendations in the present Policy Brief can only yield limited improvements toward more mixed farming and agroforestry.

A specific MiFAS in line with the EU's strategic objectives for a resilient and sustainable food system is agroforestry. Alongside MIXED, the AGROMIX project³ focused solely on agroforestry and its White Paper provides an in-depth analysis of the role of agroforestry in transforming the EU food

³ Coventry University (CAWR): AGROMIX. Available from: <https://agromixproject.eu/>

system, identifies barriers, and provides policy recommendations (Dauby et al. 2024). Similar to the MIXED policy recommendations, it calls for supportive policies to overcome challenges and scale up MiFAS/agroforestry uptake in Member States. The transition towards a more sustainable European food system is also the subject of several other studies. Agora Agriculture's recent study (Agora Agriculture 2024), whose findings largely overlap with the recommendations developed in MIXED, is just one example among many.

In line with the *Strategic Dialogue*, the recommendations are mutually supportive and are calling for actions at EU and Member States level to develop supportive policies for the uptake of MiFAS across Europe. Five policy areas need to be tackled to promote the transition to MiFAS.

4.1 Further increasing the knowledge on public goods provided by MiFAS

The performance of MiFAS in terms of efficiency, resilience and sustainability is highly context specific, and knowledge on long-term benefits is lacking for different MiFAS in specific contexts. Effective policy formulation requires consolidated knowledge about the conditions under which public goods provision from MiFAS is optimal and about financial losses or incurred costs that may need to be compensated. Although MIXED was able to provide evidence on efficiency and resilience of some MiFAS across Europe, many research questions remain open. A lack of awareness and understanding of mixed farming system approaches and their benefits in terms of public goods, as a pre-requisite to appreciation and willingness to remunerate these services, is still pervasive among the public as well as among policymakers and administrators. The lack of knowledge perpetuates a regime that encourages specialisation and prevents the appreciation of benefits of mixed farming for and by society.

The *Strategic Dialogue* identifies knowledge gaps in sustainability metrics and public goods provision across different farming models, emphasising the need for harmonised benchmarking systems and scientifically sound indicators (EC 2024, p. 41-42). It proposes transforming the FADN into a FSDN to improve farm-level sustainability assessments. Whilst large potential lies in systematically analysing such data sources regarding performance of MiFAS, enhanced data collection and inter- and transdisciplinary research will remain necessary to better evaluate the long-term economic, environmental and social effects of MiFAS.

4.1.1 Strengthen support for research to close knowledge gaps regarding MiFAS and their long-term benefits

- Increase (substantially) the funding as well as duration of purposeful research to better understand the long-term impacts and the complex range of public goods provided by different types of MiFAS, their optimal management - as well as interdependencies thereof. Long-term stakeholder engagement needs to be ensured.
- Promote transdisciplinary research through comprehensive, landscape-level approaches. Farmers should be partners at eye-level in these research initiatives, leading to on-farm participatory and long-term trials.
- Facilitate financial compensation for farmers for pilot trials and demonstrations, as well as exemptions from specific regulations that may impede research progress. E.g. maximum and minimum numbers of livestock, positive or negative lists of tree species, distances between tree rows in agroforestry.

4.1.2 Establish a system for the co-generation of knowledge between all actors in MiFAS to ensure relevance of research and increase uptake

- In addition to on-farm research trials, allocate resources for establishing lighthouse farms and landscape-scale living labs. These initiatives will enhance awareness, showcase opportunities, and facilitate research.
- Create a knowledge-sharing network, guided by a clear strategy, that includes all stakeholders—such as suppliers, farmers, processors, retailers, consumers, scientists, administrators, and policymakers, along with their respective associations.
- Encourage mutual learning and knowledge exchange among farmers regarding mixed farming practices through cross-visits, field days, and other opportunities for peer-to-peer learning.
- Build a base of existing knowledge; prepare, link and bundle research project results in an easily accessible database to strengthen synergies between projects and practical use in a systemic way.

4.1.3 Foster awareness of the public goods provided by different MiFAS

- Increase understanding in society of the value of public goods provided by MiFAS in general, and relating to local problems, e.g. soil erosion, nitrate leaching, food supply, to strengthen local capacity for action: ‘think big, act locally’.
- Implement targeted communication campaigns that highlight the varied benefits of specific mixed farming systems, such as biodiversity, soil health, carbon sequestration, building on results from research (see 4.1.1). Link the campaigns to established values and relevant ongoing discourses, such as taste, tradition, landscape value, animal welfare, ecology, and circularity. Campaigns shall be aimed at farmers, consumers, and policymakers to enhance understanding and appreciation of these systems.
- Present a balanced view that includes both benefits and drawbacks of mainstream and mixed farming systems. Be transparent about the trade-offs that must be considered.

4.2 Strengthen capacities of farmers and intermediaries

In contrast to specialised farming, MiFAS depend on knowledge about a wide range of different farming practices, e.g. specialised crop farmers often do not have the necessary expertise in animal husbandry and vice versa. Specialisation prevails in today's agriculture, resulting in varying but deep knowledge among farmers and intermediaries, including vocational training institutions and extension services. More holistic understanding of agricultural systems is needed among all actors but runs contrary to this prevalent specialisation paradigm. While, as noted above, knowledge of crop, livestock and fruit production is widely available but remains isolated or in silos, capacity building is ever more important in the face of new innovative MiFAS, which require specific as well as integrated, knowledge. This also concerns skills needed for (new) agroforestry systems, including knowledge about suitable tree species and design, as well as skills on paludiculture.

The *Strategic Dialogue* highlights the knowledge gap in diversified farming practices, noting that current vocational training systems favour specialisation over holistic system thinking (EC 2024, p. 76-78). It calls for revised education and training to support sustainable farming models.

4.2.1 Foster learning and capacity building for MiFAS in vocational training and further education

- Revise curricula in schools, technical colleges and universities, for farmers as well as related sectors (extension, administration, research etc.) to broaden subjects beyond specialisation, and to include systems perspectives.

- Provide courses for farmers open to diversification/mixed farming, to help identify farm specific options and opportunities to benefit from MiFAS. Equip both farmers and farm workers with the necessary knowledge and skills for implementation.
- Foster the proliferation of traditional agricultural knowledge, especially in the context of traditional MiFAS, and link it to system thinking.

4.2.2 Integrate the multiple aspects of MiFAS into holistic extension services

- Equip farm advisors with up-to-date, broad as well as specific MiFAS-related knowledge, including administrative aspects through short courses and further education.
- Increase the systemic understanding among advisors and trainers through improving curricula covering a broad range of different MiFAS and methods for systems analysis, and effect a culture shift from specialisation to holistic thinking
- In extension services for mixed farming, develop plans and concepts tailored to the specific farm situation, applying system thinking and considering the landscape level.
- Provide sufficient and long-term funding for independent advisory services focused on mixed farming, to span the timeframes involved and allow for long-term planning (e.g. in establishing agroforestry systems).

4.3 Taking a landscape perspective in strategies and decision making

Landscape level mixedness (for a definition, see 1.2.1) allows for the efficiency of specialised farming while improving circularity within a region, leading to greater sustainability. Interactions between farms at regional/local level can counteract tendencies toward specialisation of entire regions, e.g. the livestock clusters of northern central Europe. The multitude and diversity of interactions, as well as natural environmental conditions, call for strategies to achieve mixedness on a landscape level. Such landscape strategies are needed to be able to foster cooperation between farms, as well as value chains, in a targeted manner, and help overcome path dependencies. Demand for a variety of local and regional products can strengthen the mixedness of a landscape; the respective value chains and consumer awareness should therefore be fostered (4.5.4, 4.1.3).

The holistic view of the landscape also helps to identify possible synergies and problems, to set goals, and, by anchoring the conversation to shared interests, to overcome problems of collective action: In a landscape perspective, consequences that would be external to the farm economy perspective are, to varying degrees, internal to the system in question. This means that a shift to a landscape perspective provides both the incentives and the means to address negative externalities of farming.

Achieving landscape objectives requires strong collaboration, not only among farmers but also between farmers and other actors. This necessitates trust/social cohesion that is often lacking, making it challenging to establish and maintain collaborative mixed farming systems without the presence of external facilitation.

The *Strategic Dialogue* acknowledges the importance of regional cooperation among farmers to counteract the negative effects of specialised farming landscapes (EC 2024, p. 70-72). It emphasises that landscape-level strategies can improve sustainability and economic viability.

4.3.1 Ensure multi-level integration of strategies concerning landscapes, agriculture and land use

- Ensure integration of overarching European strategies and objectives (such as Green Deal, Biodiversity Strategy) and specific regional needs and services, particularly related to agricultural

practices impacting landscapes, into long-term landscape strategies. These strategies must be developed with involvement of all stakeholders.

4.3.2 Foster evidence-based setting of objectives and targets by increasing systemic understanding of farming systems at all relevant territorial scales

- Improve availability of information on farming systems at various levels, combining existing data sources such as FSDN, IACS, other controls and research data.
- Increase capacities of relevant actors at regional and local levels to analyse and interpret landscape level information.
- Support decision makers in analysis of existing information and needs identification through improved stakeholder participation and improved research-policy interfaces.

4.3.3 Establish territorial mechanisms that ensure an integrated approach by using synergies between farming systems

- Foster intermediaries taking the role of 'landscape coordinators' who enable interaction between farmers as well as with other actors. Equip these intermediaries with tools and methods to foster trust, facilitate matchmaking, establish agreements, and moderate conflicts across sectors, extending beyond agriculture to encompass the broader landscape.
- Foster collaboration of farmers and other actors to create synergies between farming systems and to achieve local and regional landscape objectives. Beside the above recommendation, this can take the shape of collaborative schemes as proposed in 4.5.

4.4 Improving the regulatory and administrative frameworks

MiFAS often come with certain challenges and specificities, for which the administrative systems may be ill-matched. This – together with the increased number of farming practices on a farm, which all require paperwork, as a consequence of mixed farming – can result in high administrative burden, long processing times and makes well-intentioned support schemes less attractive overall.

The *Strategic Dialogue* acknowledges **regulatory fragmentation and administrative burdens** as significant barriers to sustainable farming (EC 2024, p. 52). Agricultural and forestry policies and administrative domains remain largely separate, adding to the already complex administrative burdens and uncertainties for those attempting to integrate diverse practices, or even ruling out the implementation of MiFAS altogether. Especially the rigid separation of land uses for agriculture and forestry can be an obstacle for agroforestry.

Specific aspects of MiFAS, e.g. agroforestry, permaculture or paludiculture, come with challenges in defining the respective systems in a way that is practical for policy interventions. In the case of agroforestry, this has resulted in requirements such as minimum/maximum number of trees, positive/negative lists of species etc. The definitions and the associated requirements often leave only a narrow range of possibilities, which in conjunction with farm operations may be too restrictive. Agriculture is a long-term business, even more so in cases like agroforestry or rewetting, which, depending on the respective system, may only generate a return on investment over a long period of time (up to several decades). Therefore, it is important to ensure the long-term validity of specifications and regulatory frameworks.

A lack of integrated thinking and coherence across regulatory domains and disciplinary foci in administrative and other contexts may result in mutual obstruction. Through collaboration and active dialogue between organisational structures, stakeholders may identify solutions that are practical, economically viable, and mutually beneficial.

The need for simplified regulatory frameworks is emphasised in the *Strategic Dialogue* (EC 2024, e.g. p. 53). The necessity to minimise the administrative burden on farmers to achieve the transition to more mixed land use systems in Europe, however, must not be traded off against accountability and adherence to regulations that ensure overarching objectives, otherwise the purposes of a transition to more mixed land use would be undermined.

4.4.1 Reduce administrative burden and regulatory barriers that are hampering MiFAS

- Increase understanding of farm management and agriculture in bureaucracies to facilitate informed and farmer-oriented administrative frameworks.
- Maintain enough stability in the legal frameworks to allow for long-term commitments over planning horizons of the various MiFAS. This may include the duration of tree growth in agroforestry or the introduction of livestock on an arable farm.
- Ensure that legal frameworks, particularly those at Member State or regional level provide enough flexibility to accommodate various MiFAS, enabling farmers to tailor them to their operations, while maintaining strict adherence to intended outcomes, definitions, and requirements (e.g. nitrate directive, climate protection).
- Improve communication of administrations to farmers as well as intermediaries that focuses on essential administrative needs and obligations in a concise manner.
- Create simplified administration system interfaces and interaction processes between administration and farmers, resulting in a minimum of administrative effort.

4.4.2 Strengthen interdisciplinary integration across all organisational structures and foster active dialogue among actors to improve the coherence of policies, support mechanisms, regulative domains

- Establish and strengthen farmer organisations and other organisations in their plurality (including inter-branch organisations, levy boards, producer organisations, EIP operational groups etc.) which integrate agricultural disciplines to facilitate knowledge transfer and collaboration. As intermediaries between farmers, administrators and policy makers, these organisations can provide practical feedback on improvements in administration.
- Establish collaborative and rapid procedures and structures for communication in administration at national or sub-national level (where relevant), as well as decision-making processes, which transcend the separate domains pertinent to MiFAS.
- Develop and apply collaborative approaches involving all actors and in consideration of fundamental/essential requirements of each domain.

4.5 Promoting the long-term viability of sustainable and resilient mixed farming systems and competitive mixed farms

MiFAS can face significant challenges in terms of achieving economic viability, due to lower economies of scale, increased labour demands etc. The *Strategic Dialogue* identifies **economic viability** as a key challenge for **small and mixed farms**, emphasising **the need for targeted financial support** (p. 42-44). As of now, the complex range of public goods that MiFAS provide is not remunerated by the markets. To ensure the long-term economic viability of different MiFAS, the income foregone as compared to the specialised systems must be compensated.

Various conditions and pre-requisites need to be met for MiFAS to achieve synergies and realise their potential benefits in terms of sustainability and resilience. Decisions should be made in awareness of possible trade-offs between efficiency and other goals, where e.g. changes that would lead

to an introduction of less productive systems (or system components) are evaluated with a view to far flung and long-term consequences, including compensation effects where lost production must be made up for elsewhere. Obvious examples of overall detrimental changes include that no permanent grassland, especially on poor soils, should be ploughed, and an overall increase in the number of livestock should be avoided (a redistribution may be beneficial). Such conditions must be considered in the operationalisation of MiFAS, e.g. in selection and eligibility criteria (2.5.2, 2.5.3).

Profitability is often only reached long after the introduction of MiFAS. Some MiFAS, such as agroforestry or rewetting, are associated with significant investments due to the extensive changes in land management that they entail. Acquiring new machinery and adapting production methods or even planting trees is costly, and a barrier especially in the face of uncertainties, e.g. regarding demand, land tenure, climate, or regulations. Adequate financial support and/or compensation for farmers in the establishing phase is therefore important.

Where MiFAS are more labour intensive or less productive in terms of a marketable product, one perspective for economic viability, aside from subsidies, is raising awareness for the benefits of MiFAS and marketing in a way that emphasises these benefits. Mixedness in general may be difficult to communicate; other values and benefits of mixed production, such as animal welfare, ecology and regionality may be more compatible with customers' established preferences. If customers demand a variety of local and regional products, variety of production and therefore mixedness in a region is encouraged.

While there is some potential for specialised marketing to a sustainability-aware clientele, this approach has quantitative limitations. If the benefits of MiFAS are to be obtained at a larger scale, their respective products will have to be incorporated into existing processing and marketing channels that deal with large amounts of agricultural goods with less regard to their origin and method of production.

The *Strategic Dialogue* demands that transformation of the CAP should be 'a stepwise and planned approach considering the long-term investment cycles in the sector'. The transition should be funded by mobilising both public and private capital (EC 2024, p. 46). The installation of a complementary and temporary 'Just Transition Fund' should support the transition of the entire agricultural sector (EC 2024, p. 43). A transition to more MiFAS depends on measures such as the following:

4.5.1 Ensure the economic viability of agricultural practices that provide most public goods

- Assess whether the existing support framework is meeting agreed commitments and objectives, ensures effective and efficient implementation, and avoids unintended outcomes. Make the necessary adjustments to follow the principle *public money for public goods* and align it with expectations for agri-food system transformation.

4.5.2 Provide support for transition to more MiFAS

- Include selection criteria that favour mixedness at farm and/or landscape level in investment support schemes. The investment support schemes need to allow for the diverse investment needs relating to the establishment of MiFAS.
- Include elements in relation to the regeneration and restoration of traditional MiFAS in investment support programmes.
- Develop support schemes that cover additional costs (such as increased labour and lacking economies of scale) and/or lower income specifically for the transition period to MiFAS.

4.5.3 Support the ongoing management of MiFAS

- Introduce (selection or eligibility) criteria that favour MiFAS at the farm as well as inter-farm scale in agri-environmental support schemes to compensate for farm-economic disadvantages.
- The framework as proposed in 5.1.1 shall support landscape-level mixedness, allowing farmers to jointly apply for support measures to encourage collective action, foster collaboration, and maximise synergies from multi-functional land use. The existing cooperation incentive Support schemes should cover transaction costs of cooperation.

4.5.4 Foster value chains for MiFAS products

- Promote measures that strengthen the market positions of MiFAS producers, e.g. cooperatives to pool inputs, storage, processing, and selling (as well as knowledge and machinery). This helps offset drawbacks of smaller individual production systems.

5 Conclusions on transition pathways towards resilient and efficient MiFAS

The MIXED project found some variable results, with the only viable conclusion being that the efficiency and resilience of specific mixed farming practices are highly context-specific, and their benefits can only be accurately assessed when compared to non-mixed farms within the same or similar contexts. The assessment of efficiency and resilience of mixed farming, referred to as 'mixedness', was conducted at both the farm level and the landscape (and value chain) level, resulting in significantly different outcomes.

The policy frameworks across countries participating in MIXED – even for those being part of the European Union with its most relevant CAP – are diverse, influenced by unique historical, cultural, and socio-economic factors. This variation necessitates a tailored approach to policy recommendations, as a one-size-fits-all solution is often impractical. Some specific insights into the respective countries covered in the project were collected in the back casting workshops, where detailed discussions and analyses of national specificities were conducted. These workshops offered a deeper understanding of the unique contexts and policy environments within each Member State, facilitating more precise and effective policy development. Specificities at sub-national scales, in agricultural policy in the more federal Member States, in natural conditions, value chains and demand, traditional farming practices and the resulting cultural landscapes, also need to be taken into consideration. Consequently, we provide general policy recommendations that aim to address common challenges and opportunities across Europe. The objective of a more mixed agricultural landscape is served well by subsidiarity in all relating policy fields.

It becomes evident that intermediary organisations and persons play a crucial role in facilitating transitions to mixed practices at various levels, including farm, inter-farm, and landscape levels. Ideally, these intermediaries can consider all perspectives and effectively communicate landscape-level demands to farmers. However, the MIXED project did not focus on evaluating the social, societal, or environmental benefits, such as biodiversity conservation, of mixed farming practices. As a result, many questions remain unanswered regarding a comprehensive assessment of the contributions to resilience and sustainability, and the results of this project cannot obviate further assessments of specific practices in their contexts, as a pre-requisite for designing effective support policies tailored to specific goals at the national and sub-national levels of policymaking.

5.1 Transition Pathways to more MiFAS

The transition to more resilient, efficient and sustainable MiFAS requires three intertwined pathways of actions. The existing barriers for an uptake of MiFAS need to be removed or at least reduced. Actors need to be supported to set up new MiFAS, and all levels of governance need to be actively engaged in steering the implementation of MiFAS.

Figure 2 Schematic illustration of the transition pathways to more MiFAS

Enable practicing MiFAS

To facilitate the widespread adoption of MiFAS, policy frameworks must become more flexible and supportive. Current regulations often impose rigid land-use distinctions between agriculture and forestry, limiting farmers' ability to implement diversified systems. Simplifying administrative procedures, harmonising agricultural and environmental policies, and providing regulatory clarity will reduce barriers to MiFAS adoption. Policymakers should integrate MiFAS considerations into existing frameworks, ensuring that farmers can transition to mixed systems without excessive bureaucratic constraints.

Beyond regulatory adjustments, building farmers' capacities is essential. MiFAS require broad knowledge across crop production, livestock integration, and agroforestry management, which is not adequately covered in current vocational training programs. Updating agricultural education to include systems-thinking approaches and sustainability-focused curricula will help bridge this gap. Advisory services must be expanded and trained in MiFAS-specific knowledge to provide tailored guidance to farmers. Additionally, peer-to-peer learning, field demonstrations, and farmer-led research initiatives should be supported to enhance knowledge-sharing and practical implementation.

Recognising the public goods provided by MiFAS—such as biodiversity enhancement, improved soil health, and carbon sequestration—is key to ensuring financial viability for farmers. Policies should incentivise these benefits through annual payments or targeted subsidies. CAP funding structures should be adjusted to prioritise MiFAS, ensuring that farmers are compensated for their contributions to sustainability. Raising public awareness about the benefits of MiFAS can also help drive market demand for diversified, regionally produced agricultural products.

Support establishment of new MiFAS

Transitioning to MiFAS may require significant initial investments, or conversely, exiting from capital intensive existing enterprise such as intensive livestock production can pose a challenge to the economics of a farm. Support mechanisms should include direct investment grants, low-interest loans, and risk-sharing financial instruments tailored to the diverse needs of mixed farming systems. Agroforestry, in particular, involves long-term commitments with slow financial returns, necessitating stable and long-term funding frameworks. Investment support should also extend to cooperative infrastructure, enabling farmers to share resources for storage, processing, and distribution, thereby increasing the economic viability of MiFAS.

Beyond financial support, technical guidance is critical for the successful establishment of MiFAS. Advisory services must be strengthened to offer farm-specific recommendations on diversified land-use planning, resource cycling, and ecological management. Digital decision-support tools can assist farmers in evaluating different MiFAS models and their economic feasibility. Additionally, research institutions should collaborate with farmers to develop best practices, conduct on-farm trials, and establish demonstration sites that showcase successful MiFAS implementation.

Encouraging cooperation among farms will further enhance the effectiveness of MiFAS. Shared land-use strategies, nutrient cycling networks, and collective marketing initiatives can improve resource efficiency and increase farm resilience. Financial incentives should be offered for collaborative approaches, enabling farmers to jointly apply for funding and policy support. Regional networks and farmer cooperatives should be facilitated to foster trust, knowledge exchange, and coordinated decision-making, ultimately driving the large-scale adoption of MiFAS.

Steer MiFAS implementation

For MiFAS to be successfully integrated into European agriculture, targeted policy measures must be implemented at the regional and national levels. Identifying priority areas where MiFAS can have the most significant environmental and economic impact—such as regions facing soil degradation, water shortages, or biodiversity loss—will allow for strategic resource allocation. Land-use planning policies should incorporate MiFAS, ensuring that diversified farming systems receive targeted support within designated areas.

Policy measures should also focus on specific farm types and production systems that stand to benefit the most from MiFAS. Small and medium-sized farms often face higher barriers to transitioning, requiring tailored financial aid and technical support. Similarly, product-specific support mechanisms should be introduced to encourage value chain development for MiFAS-related outputs, such as agroforestry timber, integrated crop-livestock products, and regionally produced organic food.

Strengthening market access for MiFAS products is essential for long-term economic viability. Policies should support cooperative marketing strategies, direct sales initiatives, and value chain integration to ensure that farmers can sell their diversified products profitably. Public procurement programs should prioritise MiFAS products, creating stable demand and increasing consumer awareness of the benefits of mixed farming. By aligning funding, policy support, and market incentives, MiFAS can be positioned as a key component of sustainable European agriculture.

5.2 Coordinating actions across multiple stakeholder groups

A successful transition to MiFAS requires coordinated actions across multiple stakeholder groups. Below is an outline of the key target groups and corresponding actions to enable, support, and steer MiFAS adoption.

Farmers (Current and Prospective MiFAS Practitioners)

Farmers play of course the central role in the transition towards MiFAS, requiring financial, technical, and knowledge-based support. To facilitate adoption, financial incentives such as transition grants, low-interest loans, and annual payments for ecosystem services must be provided to offset initial costs and compensate for potential income fluctuations. Training programs should be expanded to include integrated crop-livestock systems, agroforestry, and regenerative farming practices, equipping farmers with the skills to manage diversified systems effectively. Strengthening advisory services with specialised knowledge in MiFAS will ensure that farmers receive farm-specific guidance on implementation, risk management, and regulatory compliance. Additionally, digital decision-support tools can help farmers assess the viability of different MiFAS models and optimise farm management strategies. Farmer-led research, on-farm trials, and peer-to-peer knowledge exchange initiatives should be promoted, allowing farmers to learn from practical experiences and adapt MiFAS approaches to their specific contexts.

Farm Advisors and Extension Services

Advisors and extension services are crucial in supporting farmers in their transition to MiFAS by providing technical expertise and strategic guidance. These professionals need specialised training on MiFAS principles, including crop-livestock integration, agroforestry design, and landscape-level management. Developing methodologies for systems analysis and risk assessment will allow advisors to provide farmers with holistic recommendations tailored to their farm conditions. Extension services should facilitate on-farm training programs and demonstration projects, showcasing successful MiFAS practices to encourage adoption. Additionally, knowledge-sharing platforms should be established to enable advisors across different regions to exchange best practices and lessons learned, ensuring continuous improvement in advisory support for mixed farming systems.

Cooperatives and Farmer Networks

Farmer cooperatives and networks play a vital role in overcoming barriers to MiFAS adoption by fostering collaboration and resource-sharing among farms. Supporting the development of cooperative business models will enable farmers to pool resources, reduce costs, and collectively invest in infrastructure such as storage, processing facilities, and marketing platforms. Encouraging regional cooperation among farms for nutrient cycling, rotational grazing, and shared machinery can enhance efficiency and sustainability. Additionally, cooperatives should be empowered to facilitate joint applications for funding and policy support, streamlining access to financial resources. Strengthening local and regional farmer networks will also enhance trust-building, collective problem-solving, and the development of sustainable value chains for MiFAS products.

Policymakers and Administrators (EU, National, Regional Levels)

Policymakers and administrators must create an enabling environment for MiFAS by reforming regulatory frameworks and ensuring financial support for farmers transitioning to mixed systems. Simplifying administrative procedures and reducing bureaucratic barriers will make MiFAS adoption more accessible. Aligning agricultural, forestry, and environmental policies is crucial to avoid regulatory contradictions that hinder integrated farming approaches. The CAP should be restructured to include targeted MiFAS support, with long-term funding mechanisms that recognise the slow return

on investment of agroforestry and diversified systems. Regionalised land-use policies should prioritise MiFAS in areas where they can provide the most significant environmental and economic benefits, ensuring targeted support and incentivising adoption. Public procurement policies should be adjusted to prioritise MiFAS products, creating stable markets and encouraging farmers to transition.

Financial Institutions and Investors

Financial institutions and investors must develop tailored financial products to facilitate MiFAS adoption. Investment grants, low-interest loans, and risk-sharing mechanisms will help farmers manage the financial risks associated with transitioning from specialised to diversified systems on all levels. Green finance initiatives and sustainability-linked funding should be expanded to support MiFAS, recognising the environmental benefits they provide. Additionally, insurance schemes should be designed to mitigate financial risks related to climate variability and changes in market demand. Blended finance models, where public and private funding sources are combined, can provide long-term security for farmers investing in MiFAS, ensuring that the transition is financially viable.

Researchers and Educational Institutions

Research institutions and universities must generate scientific evidence on the long-term sustainability and economic viability of MiFAS to guide policy decisions and farm-level implementation. Conducting inter- and transdisciplinary research on soil health, biodiversity benefits, and productivity outcomes in different MiFAS models will provide valuable insights for farmers and policymakers. Agricultural curricula should be revised to incorporate systems-thinking approaches, ensuring that future farmers, advisors, and administrators are trained in mixed farming principles. Universities and research organizations should also collaborate with farmers to establish on-farm research trials and living labs, facilitating real-world testing of innovative MiFAS practices. Additionally, harmonised sustainability indicators should be developed to benchmark MiFAS performance and inform policy frameworks.

Consumers and Retailers

Consumers and retailers play a critical role in supporting the economic viability of MiFAS through demand for sustainably produced food. Raising consumer awareness about the benefits of MiFAS, including biodiversity conservation, soil regeneration, and climate resilience, will create market incentives for farmers to transition. Certification and labeling schemes that recognise MiFAS products should be introduced, helping consumers make informed purchasing decisions. Direct-to-consumer sales models, such as farmers' markets and community-supported agriculture (CSA) programs, can enhance economic returns for MiFAS farmers. Large retailers should be encouraged to integrate MiFAS products into their supply chains, ensuring market stability. Public campaigns emphasising the regional and ecological advantages of MiFAS products will further drive consumer interest and market demand.

Landscape and Regional Planners

Landscape and regional planners must integrate MiFAS into long-term land-use strategies to optimise sustainability and resilience at the landscape level. Identifying priority regions where MiFAS can address soil degradation, water scarcity, or biodiversity loss will allow for targeted policy interventions. Strengthening cooperation among farms at the landscape scale will enable circular systems, such as coordinated livestock grazing, shared agroforestry corridors, and regionalised nutrient cycling. Policymakers should provide incentives for landscape-scale transitions, encouraging collective action among farmers and other land managers. Additionally, creating regional coordination mechanisms will ensure that MiFAS policies and support measures align with local environmental and economic priorities.

5.3 Outlook on the future of agricultural policy in the EU

This report and policy recommendations build on insights on challenges and barriers of a transition to resilient and efficient MiFAS in the current policy frameworks. After a transition period, the Member States of the European Union started to implement the current CAP only in 2023. The effects that policy changes in this current period have brought about might not have become evident yet. However, many of the challenges and issues related to the policy framework remain from previous periods. Organisations and researchers have long been calling for a shift away from area payments towards payments for public goods provided and towards a reduction in livestock numbers. This necessity has also become apparent in the MIXED project and continues to be the case.

However, we are still in the middle of the current funding period of the CAP (2023-2027) and only in 2025 a first performance review of each CAP strategic plans will be able to show effects of this policy, especially of newly introduced interventions such as the eco-schemes. Member States and the European Commission (EC) are however, already preparing for the new CAP after 2027.

In February 2025, the EC presented its *Vision for Agriculture and Food* (EC 2025), outlining the strategic direction by focussing on the attractiveness, generational renewal, competitiveness and innovation of the agricultural sector. Building only partly on the recommendations of the *Strategic Dialogue on the Future of Agriculture* and also less on the sustainability aspects of the Green Deal and/or the Farm-to-Fork Strategy, it was quickly met with scepticism, especially regarding the conservation and protection of natural resources and public goods (e.g. Fortuna and Lory 2025, Slow Food Foundation 2025).

In conjunction with its *Vision for Agriculture and Food*, and to provide advice on policy developments and in preparation of future policy initiatives, the EC has formed a *European Board on Agriculture and Food* (EBAF), appointing 30 member organisations to represent the rural and farming community, other actors active in the food supply chain, and civil society. It should also contribute to create trust and multi-stakeholder participation.

Concurrently, discussions are intensifying around the restructuring of the Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF), with leaked proposals suggesting significant shifts in funding allocations to better support sustainable agricultural practices.

Given the ongoing CAP reform process and the potential shifts outlined in the leaked MFF proposal, the MIXED policy recommendations are timely and well-positioned to inform the next CAP framework, ensuring a more resilient, sustainable, and integrated agricultural future for Europe.

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Extract of the top-down approach in T6.4: Greenhouse gas emission taxes encourage mixing in the livestock sector - A simulation analysis of Swedish dairy farms

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Introduction

A third of anthropogenic greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions can be attributed to the food system, with livestock agriculture as a major driver (Crippa et al., 2021). Therefore, there are large-scale efforts worldwide to mitigate GHG emissions from livestock agriculture. To do so, livestock farmers may scale back livestock production and/or adopt technologies to reduce GHG emissions per output. Examples of the latter include emission-reducing floors in stables, improved feed, improved circularity, precision fertilization, and fossil fuel-efficient technologies.

From the policy side, one may facilitate reduction of GHG emissions via advisory services and economic instruments, such as a cap-and-trade program, subsidies and taxes. This part of D6.4 focuses is on the potential impact of economic instruments, in this case taxes.

Denmark has recently decided to implement a GHG emission tax system, which is unique, as the agricultural sector is hitherto exempt from any regulations for mitigating GHG emissions. Given the geographical and cultural proximity with the Danish context, we simulate the impact of GHG emission taxes on production behaviour in Swedish dairy farms. In line with the application of Sørensen et al. (2025) to Danish agriculture, we simulate the effect of a GHG emission tax of €100 per ton of CO₂-eq on the polluting inputs. We contribute by developing a new production model that appropriately accounts for the by-production of GHG emissions. Using data envelopment analysis (DEA), we rely on the by-production approach of Murty et al. (2012). This approach represents the state-of-the-art of accurately modelling pollution in a production framework. Furthermore, we use the approach of Ang and Kerstens (2016) to verify the land reallocation under such a tax. This allows us to assess the potential impact on the mixedness of a GHG emission tax.

Method

Technology set

A vector of input quantities $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_N) \in \mathbb{R}_+^N$ is transformed to a vector of output quantities $\mathbf{y} = (y_1, \dots, y_M) \in \mathbb{R}_+^M$. The production process also generates GHG emissions $b \geq 0$. Let us define the following technology set (Murty et al., 2012):

$$T = \{(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, b) : \mathbf{x} \text{ can produce } (\mathbf{y}, b)\} \quad (1)$$

Following Ang and Kerstens (2016) and Wang et al. (2023), T consists of the intersection of the livestock sub-technology, T_L , the crop sub-technology, T_C , and the polluting sub-technology, T_{GHG} :

$$T = T_L \cap T_C \cap T_{GHG} \quad (2)$$

The livestock sub-technology is defined as:

$$T_L = \left\{ \left(\mathbf{x}_L^v, \mathbf{x}_L^f, \mathbf{x}_j^v, \mathbf{x}_j^f, A_L, \mathbf{y}_L \right) : \left(\mathbf{x}_L^v, \mathbf{x}_L^f, \mathbf{x}_j^v, \mathbf{x}_j^f, A_L \right) \text{ can produce } \mathbf{y}_L \right\}, \quad (3)$$

where the subscript L indicates livestock specificity, and the subscript j indicates joint inputs that are shared in the livestock production and crop production. The superscript v indicates variable inputs, and the subscript f indicates fixed inputs for which the level is assumed to be unchangeable in the short run. A_L is the land area (input) dedicated to livestock production. In line with for example Färe and Primont (1995), the inputs and outputs are assumed to be strongly disposable, and T_L is assumed to be bounded, closed, and convex.

The crop sub-technology is defined as:

$$T_C = \left\{ \left(\mathbf{x}_C^v, \mathbf{x}_C^f, \mathbf{x}_j^v, \mathbf{x}_j^f, A_C, \mathbf{y}_C \right) : \left(\mathbf{x}_C^v, \mathbf{x}_C^f, \mathbf{x}_j^v, \mathbf{x}_j^f, A_C \right) \text{ can produce } \mathbf{y}_C \right\}, \quad (4)$$

where the subscript C indicates crop specificity. As before, the subscript j indicates joint inputs that are shared in the livestock production and crop production, the superscript v indicates variable inputs, and the subscript f indicates fixed. A_C is the land area dedicated to livestock production. Also here, the inputs and outputs are assumed to be strongly disposable, and T_C is assumed to be bounded, closed, and convex.

The polluting sub-technology is defined as:

$$T_{GHG} = \left\{ \left(\mathbf{x}_L^{v,p}, \mathbf{x}_C^{v,p}, \mathbf{x}_j^{v,p}, b \right) : \left(\mathbf{x}_L^{v,p}, \mathbf{x}_C^{v,p}, \mathbf{x}_j^{v,p} \right) \text{ can produce } b \right\}, \quad (5)$$

where the superscript p indicates the (sub-)vector of polluting variable inputs. Let $\left(\mathbf{x}_C^{v,np}, \mathbf{x}_C^{v,np}, \mathbf{x}_j^{v,np} \right)$ be the (sub-)vector of non-polluting variable inputs. Following Murty et al. (2012), $\left(\mathbf{x}_L^{v,p}, \mathbf{x}_C^{v,p}, \mathbf{x}_j^{v,p}, b \right)$ is assumed to be costly disposable.

The livestock efficiency is $D_O^L \left(\mathbf{x}_L^v, \mathbf{x}_L^f, \mathbf{x}_j^v, \mathbf{x}_j^f, A_L, \mathbf{y}_L \right)^{-1}$, where

$$D_O^L \left(\mathbf{x}_L^v, \mathbf{x}_L^f, \mathbf{x}_j^v, \mathbf{x}_j^f, A_L, \mathbf{y}_L \right) = \sup_{\theta} \left\{ \theta > 0 : \left(\mathbf{x}_L^v, \mathbf{x}_L^f, \mathbf{x}_j^v, \mathbf{x}_j^f, A_L, \theta \mathbf{y}_L \right) \in T_L \right\} \forall \mathbf{x}_L^v, \mathbf{x}_L^f, \mathbf{x}_j^v, \mathbf{x}_j^f, A_L \quad (6)$$

Here, $D_O^L(\cdot)^{-1}$ with a value (0,1] indicates the extent to which the farm succeeds at achieving high levels of \mathbf{y}_L , given $\left(\mathbf{x}_L^v, \mathbf{x}_L^f, \mathbf{x}_j^v, \mathbf{x}_j^f, A_L \right)$.

The crop efficiency is $D_O^C \left(\mathbf{x}_C^v, \mathbf{x}_C^f, \mathbf{x}_j^v, \mathbf{x}_j^f, A_C, \mathbf{y}_C \right)^{-1}$, where

$$D_O^C \left(\mathbf{x}_C^v, \mathbf{x}_C^f, \mathbf{x}_j^v, \mathbf{x}_j^f, A_C, \mathbf{y}_C \right) = \sup_{\theta} \left\{ \theta > 0 : \left(\mathbf{x}_C^v, \mathbf{x}_C^f, \mathbf{x}_j^v, \mathbf{x}_j^f, A_C, \theta \mathbf{y}_C \right) \in T_C \right\} \forall \mathbf{x}_C^v, \mathbf{x}_C^f, \mathbf{x}_j^v, \mathbf{x}_j^f, A_C \quad (7)$$

Here, $D_O^C(\cdot)^{-1}$ with a value (0,1] indicates the extent to which the farm succeeds at achieving high levels of \mathbf{y}_C , given $\left(\mathbf{x}_C^v, \mathbf{x}_C^f, \mathbf{x}_j^v, \mathbf{x}_j^f, A_C \right)$.

The GHG emission efficiency is $D_I^{GHG} \left(\mathbf{x}_L^{v,p}, \mathbf{x}_C^{v,p}, \mathbf{x}_j^{v,p}, b \right)$, where

$$D_I^{GHG} \left(\mathbf{x}_L^{v,p}, \mathbf{x}_C^{v,p}, \mathbf{x}_j^{v,p}, b \right) = \inf_{\gamma} \left\{ \gamma > 0 : \left(\mathbf{x}_L^{v,p}, \mathbf{x}_C^{v,p}, \mathbf{x}_j^{v,p}, \gamma b \right) \in T_C \right\} \forall \mathbf{x}_L^{v,p}, \mathbf{x}_C^{v,p}, \mathbf{x}_j^{v,p} \quad (8)$$

Here, $D_I^{GHG}(\cdot)$ with a value (0,1] indicates the extent to which the farm succeeds at achieving low levels of b , given $\left(\mathbf{x}_L^{v,p}, \mathbf{x}_C^{v,p}, \mathbf{x}_j^{v,p} \right)$.

Impact of GHG emission taxes

Let us first consider the scenario in which there are no taxes. Let the vector $(\mathbf{w}_C^v, \mathbf{w}_L^v, \mathbf{w}_j^v, \mathbf{p}_L, \mathbf{p}_C)$ be the (strictly positive) prices that correspond with $(\mathbf{x}_C^v, \mathbf{x}_L^v, \mathbf{x}_j^v, \mathbf{y}_L, \mathbf{y}_C)$. Our data is described as:

$$\mathbf{S} = \{\mathbf{x}_{kt}, \mathbf{y}_{kt}, b_{kt}\}_{t=1}^T \quad (9)$$

for farm $k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$. The farm under evaluation is indexed by i in period t .

Using data envelopment analysis (DEA), the profit maximization problem without GHG emission taxes can be formulated as:

$$\begin{aligned} & \pi(\mathbf{w}_{C,it}^v, \mathbf{w}_{L,it}^v, \mathbf{w}_{j,it}^v, \mathbf{p}_{L,it}, \mathbf{p}_{C,it}, \mathbf{x}_{L,it}^f, \mathbf{x}_{C,it}^f) \\ = & \sup_{\substack{\mathbf{x}_{L,it}^{v,*}, \mathbf{y}_{C,it}^{v,*}, \mathbf{x}_{j,it}^{v,*}, \mathbf{y}_{L,it}^{v,*}, \mathbf{y}_{C,it}^{v,*}, A_{L,it}^*, A_{C,it}^*, b_{it}^*, \lambda_{kt}, \mu_{kt}, \omega_{kt}}} \mathbf{p}_{L,it} \mathbf{y}_{L,it}^* + \mathbf{p}_{C,it} \mathbf{y}_{C,it}^* - \mathbf{w}_{L,it}^v \mathbf{x}_{L,it}^{v,*} - \mathbf{w}_{C,it}^v \mathbf{x}_{C,it}^{v,*} - \mathbf{w}_{j,it}^v \mathbf{x}_{j,it}^{v,*} \quad (10) \end{aligned}$$

s.t.

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \lambda_{kt} \mathbf{x}_{L,kt}^v \leq \mathbf{x}_{L,it}^{v,*} \quad (10.1)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \lambda_{kt} \mathbf{x}_{L,kt}^f \leq \mathbf{x}_{L,it}^f \quad (10.2)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \lambda_{kt} \mathbf{x}_{j,kt}^v \leq \mathbf{x}_{j,it}^{v,*} \quad (10.3)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \lambda_{kt} \mathbf{x}_{j,kt}^f \leq \mathbf{x}_{j,it}^f \quad (10.4)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \lambda_{kt} A_{L,kt} \leq A_{L,it}^* \quad (10.5)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \lambda_{kt} D_O^L(\cdot)_{it}^{-1} \mathbf{y}_{L,kt} \leq \mathbf{y}_{L,it}^* \quad (10.6)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \lambda_{kt} = 1 \quad (10.7)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \mu_{kt} \mathbf{x}_{C,kt}^v \leq \mathbf{x}_{C,it}^{v,*} \quad (10.8)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \mu_{kt} \mathbf{x}_{C,kt}^f \leq \mathbf{x}_{C,it}^f \quad (10.9)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \mu_{kt} \mathbf{x}_{j,kt}^v \leq \mathbf{x}_{j,it}^{v,*} \quad (10.10)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \mu_{kt} \mathbf{x}_{j,kt}^f \leq \mathbf{x}_{j,it}^f \quad (10.11)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \mu_{kt} A_{C,kt} \leq A_{C,it}^* \quad (10.12)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \mu_{kt} D_O^C(\cdot)_{it}^{-1} \mathbf{y}_{C,kt} \leq \mathbf{y}_{C,it}^* \quad (10.13)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \mu_{kt} = 1 \quad (10.14)$$

$$A_{L,it}^* + A_{C,it}^* = A_{L,it} + A_{C,it} \quad (10.15)$$

Let us now consider the case with GHG emission taxes. Following Sørensen et al. (2025), the tax is imposed on the polluting inputs, as GHG emissions are measured indirectly. Specifically, the tax is €100 per ton of CO₂-eq on the polluting inputs. Let $(\boldsymbol{\tau}_{L,kt}^{v,p}, \boldsymbol{\tau}_{C,kt}^{v,p}, \boldsymbol{\tau}_{j,kt}^{v,p})$ be the respective tax for $(\mathbf{x}_{L,kt}^{v,p}, \mathbf{x}_{C,kt}^{v,p}, \mathbf{x}_{j,kt}^{v,p})$, such that $(\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{L,kt}^{v,p}, \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{C,kt}^{v,p}, \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{j,kt}^{v,p}) \equiv (\mathbf{w}_{L,kt}^{v,p} + \boldsymbol{\tau}_{L,kt}^{v,p}, \mathbf{w}_{C,kt}^{v,p} + \boldsymbol{\tau}_{C,kt}^{v,p}, \mathbf{w}_{j,kt}^{v,p} + \boldsymbol{\tau}_{j,kt}^{v,p})$.

Using DEA, the profit maximization problem with GHG emission taxes can be formulated as:

$$\begin{aligned} & \pi(\mathbf{w}_{C,it}^{v,np}, \mathbf{w}_{L,it}^{v,np}, \mathbf{w}_{j,it}^{v,np}, \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{L,kt}^{v,p}, \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{C,kt}^{v,p}, \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{j,kt}^{v,p}, \mathbf{p}_{L,it}, \mathbf{p}_{C,it}, \mathbf{x}_{L,it}^f, \mathbf{x}_{C,it}^f) \\ = & \sup_{\substack{\mathbf{x}_{L,it}^{v,**}, \mathbf{y}_{C,it}^{v,**}, \mathbf{x}_{j,it}^{v,**}, \mathbf{y}_{L,it}^{v,**}, \mathbf{y}_{C,it}^{v,**}, A_{L,it}^*, A_{C,it}^*, b_{it}^*, \lambda_{kt}, \mu_{kt}, \omega_{kt}}} \mathbf{p}_{L,it} \mathbf{y}_{L,it}^{v,**} + \mathbf{p}_{C,it} \mathbf{y}_{C,it}^{v,**} \\ & - \mathbf{w}_{L,it}^{v,np} \mathbf{x}_{L,it}^{v,np,**} - \mathbf{w}_{C,it}^{v,np} \mathbf{x}_{C,it}^{v,np,**} - \mathbf{w}_{j,it}^{v,np} \mathbf{x}_{j,it}^{v,np,**} - \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{L,kt}^{v,p} \mathbf{x}_{L,it}^{v,p,**} - \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{C,kt}^{v,p} \mathbf{x}_{C,it}^{v,p,**} - \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{j,kt}^{v,p} \mathbf{x}_{j,it}^{v,p,**} \quad (11) \end{aligned}$$

s.t.

$$(10.1) - (10.15)$$

The only difference with the scenario with taxes is thus the adjusted prices; the constraints are the same.

Let us now compute the following distance function that measures the GHG emission efficiency:

$$D_I^{GHG} \left(\mathbf{x}_L^{v,p,*(*)}, \mathbf{x}_C^{v,p,*(*)}, \mathbf{x}_j^{v,p,*(*)}, b \right) = \inf_{\gamma, \omega_{kt}} \gamma \tag{10.16}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \lambda_{kt} b_{L,kt} \leq \gamma b_{L,it} \tag{10.16}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \omega_{kt} \mathbf{x}_{L,kt}^{v,p} \geq \mathbf{x}_{L,it}^{v,p,*} \text{ (or } \mathbf{x}_{L,it}^{v,p,**}) \tag{10.17}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \omega_{kt} \mathbf{x}_{C,kt}^{v,p} \geq \mathbf{x}_{C,it}^{v,p,*} \text{ (or } \mathbf{x}_{C,it}^{v,p,**}) \tag{10.18}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \omega_{kt} \mathbf{x}_{j,kt}^{v,p} \geq \mathbf{x}_{j,it}^{v,p,*} \text{ (or } \mathbf{x}_{j,it}^{v,p,**}) \tag{10.19}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \omega_{kt} = 1 \tag{10.20}$$

We compute $D_I^{GHG}(\cdot)$ for the optimal values of polluting inputs without taxes (*; see equation (10)) and with taxes (**; see equation (11)). $1 - D_I^{GHG}(\cdot)$ indicates the potential reduction in GHG emissions without taxes and with taxes. Such a two-step approach is in line with Lamkowsky et al. (2021). Finally, we also compute the status quo scenario as a benchmark by which we use the observed value of polluting inputs.

Implications for mixedness

The greenhouse gas emission tax has an impact on the resource allocations of the farm. Following equation (10.15), one can assess the potential impact on mixedness by comparing (a) the optimal land allocation under profit maximization with taxes ($A_{L,it}^{**}, A_{C,it}^{**}$), (b) the optimal land allocation under profit maximization without taxes ($A_{L,it}^*, A_{C,it}^*$), and (c) the actual land allocation ($A_{L,it}, A_{C,it}$). Specifically, we analyze the proportion of cropland use for these three scenarios: (1) $\frac{A_{C,it}^{**}}{A_{L,it} + A_{C,it}}$, (2) $\frac{A_{C,it}^*}{A_{L,it} + A_{C,it}}$, and (3) $\frac{A_{C,it}}{A_{L,it} + A_{C,it}}$.

Data

We use the data of the Swedish Farm Economic Survey (FES), which also feeds into the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) database. The GHG emissions are computed following the procedure of Baldoni et al. (2017, 2018), who apply the guidelines of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) to the FADN database. We obtain the price indices from the EUROSTAT database. The period studied is 2015-2019. We focus on dairy farms (TF8 = 5 in FADN). Table 2 shows an overview of the variables.

Table 2: Overview of variables

Symbol	Description	Variables
$\mathbf{x}_{L,kt}^{v,p}$	Polluting variable livestock-specific inputs	Feed, Livestock
$\mathbf{x}_{C,kt}^{v,p}$	Polluting variable crop-specific inputs	Fertilisers
$\mathbf{x}_{j,kt}^{v,p}$	Polluting variable joint inputs	Energy use

Symbol	Description	Variables
$x_{L,kt}^{v,np}$	Non-polluting variable livestock-specific inputs	Veterinary costs
$x_{C,kt}^{v,np}$	Non-polluting variable crop-specific inputs	Seeds and plants, plant protection, other
$x_{j,kt}^{v,np}$	Non-polluting variable joint inputs	Hired labour
$x_{j,kt}^{f,np}$	Non-polluting fixed joint inputs	Buildings and machinery, Unpaid labour
A_L	Land area dedicated to livestock	
A_C	Land area dedicated to crops	
y_L	Livestock output	Milk, milk products, beef and veal, pigmeat, poultrymeat, sheep and goats, eggs, ewes' and goats' milk, other livestock and products
y_C	Crop output	Cereals, protein crops, crops produced for energy purpose, potatoes, sugar beets, oil-seed crops, industrial crops, flowers, forage crops, other crop output

Results and Discussion

We infer the impact of the GHG emission tax by comparing the maximum profit under equation (11) to the maximum profit under equation (10). The median profit loss is 726 EUR per farm. However, Figure 3 shows that there is substantial heterogeneity in terms of predicted profit losses.

Figure 3: Predicted Profit Losses under Profit Maximization with Taxes

Given the level of polluting inputs, the median maximum reduction of GHG emissions is 32.28% under the status quo scenario. Under profit maximization without taxes, GHG emissions can reduce on average by 35.21% (although it also increases GHG emissions due to the increase in polluting inputs for some farms). Under profit maximization with taxes, GHG emissions can reduce on average by 40.56%.

Implications for mixedness

Finally, Figure 4 analyses the mixedness in terms of land allocation for the three scenarios. One observes that a GHG emission tax would result in more mixed land allocations for this sample of dairy farms.

All in all, these results show the potential impacts of a GHG emission tax in terms of profit losses, GHG emission reduction, and change in mixedness.

Figure 4: Crop Land Proportion (1) under the status quo, (2) under profit maximization without taxes, and (3) under profit maximization with taxes.

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